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Neuromorphic Electronics for Intelligence Everywhere: Emerging Devices, Flexible Platforms, and Scalable System Architectures

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ABSTRACT

Unprecedented advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI)-assisted automation continue to drive the demand for hardware that is significantly more scalable, compact, and energy-efficient. Neuromorphic electronics, which offers event-driven and massively parallel information handling capabilities inspired by the biological cognition, provides a compelling solution, especially as emerging device technologies now enable true in-memory computation and tightly integrated sensing capabilities far beyond what CMOS alone can achieve. To keep pace with rapid progress in AI algorithms, the discovery of new functional materials and their integration into unconventional computing architectures has become a critical research frontier. This perspective highlights the potential of various classes of device technologies for next-generation neuromorphic AI hardware, showcasing key breakthroughs in robust, flexible, and conformable device platforms. Such technologies are particularly promising for resource-constrained edge platforms, such as wearable electronics, soft robotics, and autonomous embedded sensing systems. Lastly, we discuss that circuit- and system-level design must advance alongside device innovation, including robust biasing schemes, reliable peripheral integration, and scalable architectures that can support dense neuromorphic arrays. Looking forward, the field must embrace full-stack co-optimization from materials and device physics to circuits, architectures, and learning algorithms, ultimately enabling adaptive, autonomous computing embedded seamlessly into everyday environments.

1 | Introduction

With the proliferation of Internet-of-Things (IoT), our everyday life has changed fundamentally. IoT has enabled modernization by introducing automation, increasing efficiency, and improving decision-making across industries and daily life through interconnected devices that collect and exchange real-time data. It

has transformed everything from managing smart cities and energy grids to revolutionizing manufacturing processes and personalizing healthcare through remote monitoring, predictive maintenance of machinery, precision agriculture and many other domains. Introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) at each sensor node (i.e., edge-intelligence) is adding a new layer to it by making these networks of connected devices more versatile and

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self-decision making, i.e., by adding intelligence everywhere. However, all this connectivity, decision-making, and automation come at a huge price. In the currently deployed IoT and edge AI architectures, sensing and computation take place in separated locations, causing a significant data-movement among the sensing units and processors. This is unsustainable in terms of energy efficiency, latency, and capacity for processing sensor data in real time, especially in limited power environments. Additional concern for constant data shuttling is the risk of information hacking, which becomes critical in high security applications. Therefore, embedded local intelligence has become one key development target.

Pursuing AI computation in traditional hardware is another major bottleneck. Since traditional von Neumann processing paradigm relies upon sequential data processing and centralized, they create a bottleneck to real-time edge computing applications of data from sensors in a limited power environment. A new paradigm of computing has therefore become essential [1]. Here nature gives an inspiring solution. Biological neurological networks execute operations in a distributed, parallel, and event-driven fashion, i.e., a great example of hardware with embedded intelligence. Therefore, biologically inspired hardware emerges as the most efficient solution for processing large quantities of complex, unstructured data. Developing such disruptive, new device-to-system level solutions offers the opportunity to create a sustainable pathway that is based on non-critical and resource-efficient materials and their heterogeneous integration with conventional electronic hardware.

Neuromorphic or brain-like computing aims to replicate the adaptive, event-driven, and massively parallel information processing of the biological brain, thereby enabling compact and energy-efficient systems capable of real-time learning and perception [2, 3]. By merging computation and memory within the same physical substrate, neuromorphic hardware alleviates the von Neumann bottleneck that constrains data throughput and power efficiency in conventional processors. Within this paradigm, memristive devices have emerged as core enablers of brain-inspired architectures. Their conductance, which evolves according to past electrical stimuli, provides a physical analog of synaptic weight modulation. Owing to their analog tunability, non-volatility, scalability, and compatibility with conventional complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) mechanisms, memristive devices have become prime candidates for implementing hardware learning elements in large-scale neuromorphic networks [4–6]. These devices exhibit both short-term and long-term plasticity (STP/LTP), allowing them to reproduce diverse forms of biological learning and adaptation in compact, low-power circuits [7–9].

At the system level, memristor crossbar arrays enable analog vector–matrix multiplication (VMM), directly mapping neural network weights into physical conductance states of the devices [7, 9]. Such arrays inherently support spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP) and Hebbian adaptation, offering local and continuous learning at the device level [10, 11]. In parallel, hybrid CMOS–memristor architectures combine the precision of CMOS neurons with the adaptive, analog behavior of memristive synapses, achieving associative learning, unsupervised clustering, and pattern recognition with minimal energy expen-

diture [11–14]. These mixed-signal systems integrate learning and inference within the same physical space, enabling continuous adaptation to dynamic stimuli without external retraining. Through successive design iterations, these architectures have evolved into bio-plausible associative circuits capable of encoding stimulus–response relationships, such as reward, punishment, and cross-sensory correlation, thereby providing adaptive control mechanisms relevant to edge-AI, autonomous systems, and embedded neuromorphic processors (Figure 1) [8, 10, 13].

In recent years, a plethora of materials, used to fabricate memristive devices, circuits, and systems, have been investigated for neuromorphic computing. From the device side, resistive random-access memories (RRAM), based on the principle of oxide filamentary conduction, show the highest technological maturity and binary oxides like HfO_2 , TiO_2 , TaO_2 , and organic or 2D materials have been mostly used as the building block of RRAMs [15]. However, stochasticity of filamentary conductance channel formation and rupture as well as high off-current in RRAMs pose reliability challenges for large-scale, ultra-low power neuromorphic circuits. Other emerging non-volatile memory technologies, like conductance bridge random-access memories (CBRAM) [16], magnetic random-access memories (MRAM) [17], phase change memories (PCM) [18], and ferroelectric memories [19] all have shown promising memristive performance in terms of low write energy, fast access, long data retention and endurance. However, all these memristive devices, other than ferroelectric devices, operate on the principle of current-driven resistive switching, making their power consumption non-trivial. Additionally, large off-state current necessitates the need for a selector device next to each memory cell that complicates the circuit fabrication and increases the device footprint. In the following sections we will discuss some essential physics of different material-based devices and show how this insight can lead to dense neuromorphic circuits with minimal external components and process complexity. For neuromorphic computing, integration of synaptic components with neurons is necessary and therefore either heterogeneous or monolithic 3D integration technology is essential. For a more biology-inspired system that interacts with its environment, integration with sensor and sensor pre-processing units is important. Hence, choice of materials and devices needs to be aligned with a full system-level perspective.

Flexible neuromorphic refers to brain-inspired computing systems built with flexible materials that can bend and conform, unlike traditional rigid electronics. These flexible systems are designed for applications like wearable devices, soft robotics, and brain-machine interfaces, enabling better integration with biological surfaces and operation in complex environments. They aim to emulate sensory perception and learning, staying in close contact with biological tissues, like wearable health monitors, or mimicking biological systems, e.g., in robotics. Significant progress has been made so far in realizing a multitude of devices showing synaptic and neuron functions and integration of sensing and computing platforms in the form of near or in-sensor computing [20, 21] on flexible substrates. This perspective focuses on some of those key results, starting from materials and devices to their circuit and system level integrations. Finally, we point to the systems and applications, where soft molecular materials can potentially widen the horizon of embedded intelligence. We also discuss current roadblocks and future research directions for the

FIGURE 1 | A schematic illustrating neuromorphic hardware technologies (ionic, ferroelectric, intercalation, phase-change, and spintronic devices) and their integration into flexible, wearable, robotic, and autonomous sensory systems. The figure highlights the role of in-sensor computing, multimodal perception, and near-sensor AI in emerging intelligent electronics.

era where intelligence will not be confined in data centers but will be everywhere.

2 | Devices for Neuromorphic Computing

In the following section, different device classes showing promising synaptic and neuron functionalities are discussed together with their system level performance predictions, done mostly using simulation but in some cases using small scale proof-of-concept hardware integration. We divide them into separate materials classes, such as ferroelectric components, organic memristors and electrochemical transistors, 2D semiconductor-based devices, and novel architectures like source-gated transistors. Some devices with multifunctionality like sensing and memorizing are also discussed in reference to near and in-sensor computing that can bring AI close to different autonomous systems.

2.1 | Low Thermal-Budget Ferroelectric Devices for Flexible Neuromorphic Computing Platforms

Ferroelectric devices, with their non-volatile polarization switching and voltage-driven fast and robust operation, have proven themselves as strong candidates for non-volatile storage devices [19] together with tunable synapses [22] and leaky integrate and fire (LIF) neurons [23]. In contrast to conventional oxide

memristors, ferroelectric memristors intrinsically exhibit better reliability and stability due to their controllable domain switching mechanisms. Nevertheless, there remain a few typical issues that need to be addressed before ferroelectric devices become mature technology. For instance, their low voltage multibit/analog operation, thermal stability, fatigue and imprint, retention and endurance require further enhancement, especially in scaled devices or large-scale integrated circuits. Several novel engineering concepts have made it possible to achieve significant progress recently, showing a promising path forward to meet the challenges of future computing and sensing platforms.

Different ferroelectric device architectures like one-transistor-one-capacitor (1T1C) ferroelectric random-access memory (FeRAM), ferroelectric field effect transistor (FeFET), ferroelectric diodes (FD) or ferroelectric tunnel junctions (FTJ) have been used in ferroelectric memories. Figure 2 shows a schematic of different device architectures together with their operating principle and their key performance matrices. Depending on the architecture, their footprint may vary and this poses restrictions for their lateral scaling, 3D stacking and dense integration. The following sections discuss some characteristic features of different low thermal budget material and device classes to evaluate their potential in flexible and adaptive neuromorphic circuits. We discuss results from ferroelectric oxides first, which is used in technologies heading toward industry-level maturity, and propose pathways that can solve issues faced by molecular ferroelectrics, like leakage due to

FIGURE 2 | Key parameters and working principles, and various ferroelectric memory cell designs. (a) One-transistor-one-capacitor (1T1C) FeRAM cell, in which the MOSFET functions as a switch and the ferroelectric capacitor retains data in a nonvolatile manner; (b) one-transistor FeFET cell, in which the ferroelectric material layer in the gate electrode stores the charge; and (c) an FTJ, in which a shift in the polarization orientation of the ultrathin ferroelectric tunnel barrier, between two different electrodes, results in varying barrier heights for the tunneling electrons for each polarization directions, leading to resistive switching. (d–f) Representations of the respected band diagrams of different types of devices. Main benefits and drawbacks of these devices are displayed in the table. Adapted from [19] under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 License.

thinning of the film, high voltage requirements, fast write and read operations, to name but a few.

2.1.1 | Oxide Ferroelectric Devices for Heterogeneous Integration on Flexible Platform

Traditional ferroelectric devices used perovskite oxides, such as BaTiO_3 , $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Zr}_x\text{TiO}_3$ (PZT), LiNbO_3 etc. However, high processing temperature and non-compatibility with the traditional CMOS logic circuits made their integration challenging in in-memory computing (IMC) circuits, where memory and peripheral CMOS need to stay physically close. Additionally, from architectural side, FeRAMs with 1T-1C structures were hard to scale as lateral scaling needed ferroelectric thinning to maintain capacitance and, due to weakening of ferroelectricity in ultrathin traditional ferroelectric oxides, they were no longer effective in a few nm ranges. This restricted their integration density and consequently limited their upscaling. These bottlenecks restricted further developments in the field, although commercialization of FeRAM happened many decades ago. In

recent years, layer transfer technologies of single crystal oxides [24] have opened a new horizon for CMOS back-end and flexible integration of these oxides. However, layer transfer is still not a standard fabrication process in semiconductor industry and involves the high risk of introducing defects affecting device and system level reliability. To avoid these issues, CMOS compatible $\text{Hf}_{1-x}\text{Zr}_x\text{O}_2$ (HZO) has emerged as a key candidate for monolithic 3D integration with logic and sensing units. HfO_2 and ZrO_2 being industry-ready material choices with mature deposition techniques like atomic layer deposition (ALD), prompted high interest and extensive research in this field. Neuromorphic and IMC architectures developed with HZO-based devices have shown significant improvement recently [25]. One key concern for low thermal budget ferroelectric materials, is their modest remanent polarization (P_r) at < 3 V operation window that makes their integration with low-power systems challenging. In recent years, utilizing emerging approaches, such as ultrathin oxide (3 nm HZO), including an antiferroelectric layer [26], and by optimising ferro and antiferroelectricity [27], switching voltage has been brought close to 1 V, while keeping the P_r in the range of $20 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. However, understanding oxygen

vacancy related trap and defect migration mechanisms in these materials under continuous bias stress still needs significant research effort. Recoverable fatigue [28] has been reported in HZO systems. However, systems with higher leakage current are unable to sustain more than 10^7 switching cycles. Therefore, reducing the leakage current in ultrathin ferroelectric films is essential for making them suitable for neuromorphic training applications and inference tasks, especially when working at higher temperatures ($> 85^\circ\text{C}$).

HZO is also becoming a viable choice for flexible substrate integration with high quality thin film capacitor devices with 4-bit precision possible [29], while annealing is done at temperatures as low as 350°C . For efficient IMC, one essential requirement is precise control of analog states [30]. Although binary neural networks with static random-access memories (SRAMs) have been the most implemented architecture in the neuromorphic domain, SRAM footprint and memory volatility are still a bottleneck. Moving toward more energy efficient analog systems requires devices with stable multiple intermediate states and their linearity for accurate VMM, one key component for AI computation. In two-terminal devices like memristors, maintaining stable intermediate states with linearity in conductance change has been a challenge. Three terminal devices provide better control of analog states due to additional control of channel conductance with the gate bias. In this context, the next generation of synaptic transistors is in high demand. Constant scaling of transistor size necessitates the need for ultra-thin channel materials. Two-dimensional van der Waals semiconductors like MoS_2 and WSe_2 and oxide semiconductors, such as amorphous indium gallium zinc oxide (IGZO) and indium tin oxide (ITO) and have recently proved as potential solutions for the ultrathin channel semiconductors. These materials can have high carrier mobility [31], are compatible with driving voltages of advanced CMOS logic circuits, show highly uniform wafer-level film formation, flexibility when deposited on a flexible substrate, and their low process temperature overcomes the back-end-of-line (BEOL) low thermal budget or flexible substrate process limitations for 3D monolithic integration with CMOS. On a flexible mica substrate, a BEOL and flexible compatible high-performance FeFET memory device based on HZO and ultrathin ITO channels has been shown [32] that outperforms devices on rigid substrates. The FeFET display a subthreshold swing (SS) of 33 mV/decade, ON/OFF current ratio > 108 , endurance $> 10^7$ cycles, consistent memory window (~ 2.8 V), and retention > 10 years. The device's conductance modulation exhibits excellent stability and dependability under various bending situations. Handwritten digit recognition accuracy based on ANNs formed by the flexible HZO-based FeFETs showed over 90% accuracy even after prolonged bias stress of 48 k pulses.

Bending tests performed on these FeFETs revealed that the devices without any prior structural flaws in their initial state can show degradation due to mechanical stress. When the bending radius gradually decreases, the internal stress of the device increases. This resulted in the creation of stress concentration areas, which ultimately caused cracks to form and spread throughout the device. As a result, the device's performance declined and eventually failed. With a maximum energy consumption per device of 1.96 nJ during training and 4.03 pJ during inference, a memcapacitive network built with flexible

HZO on Mica demonstrated a digital recognition accuracy as high as 97.63%. On the other hand, the leakage current increased by nearly an order of magnitude in the bent situation [33].

Both above results confirm that although excellent performance can be obtained from HfO_2 based flexible ferroelectric devices, repeated mechanical stress impacts their performance. Therefore, for enhancing the reliability of flexible ferroelectric devices, more structurally flexible materials, like polymeric or 2D ferroelectric, could be more beneficial. The following section discusses some state-of-the-art works in this direction.

2.1.2 | Polymer Ferroelectric Devices for Flexible Neuromorphic Systems

Polymer ferroelectrics, especially poly(vinylidene fluoride-trifluoroethylene), P(VDF-TrFE), is a versatile, low-temperature, solution-processable molecular ferroelectric [34, 35] that has the capability of becoming a reliable building block for neuromorphic hardware. Low-temperature processing and mechanical resilience allow application in skin-conformal and textile-integrated synapses and neurons. Polymer ferroelectrics underpin “soft” neuromorphic electronics that maintain analog memory under strain and bending due to their stable polarization properties with mechanical compliance. They enable nonvolatile, analog memory performance and synaptic dynamics [20], even optically active device platforms, and due to their piezo and pyroelectric properties, include human skin-like static and dynamic touch, vibration and temperature sensing, making them suitable for in-sensor computing systems.

Ferroelectric polymers are compatible with large area electronics and bio interfaces. Their gradual polarization switching modulates channel conductance in FeFETs or barrier height in FTJs continuously, giving analog weight updates with low energy per event, while the soft form factor enables wearable and conformable computing. Recent reviews show progress from single synapse results to array level performance evaluation, and hybrid systems like flexible, in-sensor vision systems and the outstanding challenges that separate elegant single devices from reliable, full-scale hardware systems [36, 37]. Due to piezo and pyroelectric behavior of the polymer, PVDF and its derivatives found applications [38] in pressure and temperature sensing and in energy harvesting, making them attractive for self-powered intelligent systems as well where energy harvesting from human motion can power a smart health monitoring system [39].

Beyond bendability and stretchability, benefits of P(VDF-TrFE) and other flexible polymers are their uniform ultrathin coverage [20] that made P(VDF-TrFE) a promising ferroelectric for FTJ [40] and FeFET [41] based synaptic devices. However, P(VDF-TrFE) has a high coercive field, E_C (~ 0.5 – 1 MV/cm) and saturation polarization is low (< 10 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$). To improve ferroelectricity, a strong β -phase is preferred that is achievable via solvent/annealing control. By annealing at $\sim 140^\circ\text{C}$ in DMF or MEK-processed films, a high β -phase fraction, P_r and cycling stability was found. Composite dielectrics and ion-assisted formulations have proven to tune switching thresholds and linearize weight updates [41, 42]. To reduce E_C , strategies similar to

FIGURE 3 | The Polymeric FTJ memristor. (a) The most common polymer P (VDF-TrFE). (b) MFS FTJ band diagram schematic example. The formation of a Schottky barrier results from electrons in the n-type semiconductor depleting from the interface when the polarization points away from the semiconducting Nb-doped SrTiO₃ electrode (lower panels). This leaves behind positively charged immobile donor ions (blue dots) that screen the bound polarization charges in P(VDF-TrFE) (minus signs). The Schottky barrier is eliminated (top panels) when polarization reverses and electrons build up at the semiconductor-ferroelectric interface (red dots). (c) PFM amplitude and phase reversal of an ultrathin (3 nm) P(VDF-TrFE) layer demonstrating that the material experiences low voltage local switching (d) PFM phase images of a P(VDF-TrFE) film area that are subsequently written by subjecting the scanning probe tip to +5, +2, -2, and -5 V. Net perpendicular polarization is shown by the blue arrows. (e) The MFS FTJ gadget exhibits multiple intermediate resistance states when scanned over various voltage ranges. a–e) Reproduced under the terms of CC-BY license from [22] Copyright 2019, The Author(s).

oxides, like mixture of anti-ferro (or relaxor ferroelectric) and ferro-polymers can be beneficial. Figure 3 shows molecular structure, operating principle of metal-ferroelectric-semiconductor (MFS) FTJ, piezo force microscope (PFM) data from a 3 nm P(VDF-TrFE) films, showing low voltage switching is possible in ultrathin P(VDF-TrFE) films.

2.1.2.1 | Ferroelectric Memristive FTJs. Two terminal memristors are preferred device choice due to their low footprint of $4F^2$ that makes it possible to make dense integration of these components in a neural network. However, this advantage comes at the cost of less controllability of device conductance, leakage or sneak current paths, analog states and device ON/OFF ratio. Additionally, due to the thicker ferroelectric layer, the operating voltage of the devices can be ~ 20 V, which is impractical for any wearable electronics. To reduce the operating voltage, thinning ferroelectric layers is important. Thin P(VDF-TrFE) layers sandwiched between electrodes in the form of ferroelectric diodes or FTJs, both can work as memristive components. However, polymer ferroelectric diodes are rarely proposed for neuromorphic computing. FTJs, in comparison, are studied intensively. It has been shown that FTJs with a semiconducting electrode [20, 21] can yield nonvolatile, multilevel conductance states. MFS junctions show a large memory window, arising from electric field induced polarization switching, leading to simultaneous barrier height and width modulation (Figure 3), resulting in higher conductance for one polarization direction compared to the opposite direction. The challenge with planar metal-ferroelectric-metal (MFM) FTJs having a moderate ON/OFF ratio was solved using the MFS junctions [43], or in MFM structures based on asymmetric coplanar nanogap-

separated metal electrodes have been employed to achieve high rectification ratios and giant tunneling electroresistance ($>10^6\%$) in P(VDF-TrFE) FTJ devices without the need for ultra-thin polymer layers, as the conduction is dominated by the nanogap channel length. [40] In MFS FTJs based on P(VDF-TrFE) have shown promising performances as low voltage operating, fast analog memory and synaptic weight elements [20, 44]. Thanks to the rich polarization switching dynamics, devices show reliable program/erase endurance ($>10^4$ cycles), retention $\geq 10^4$ s even at elevated temperature (80°C), and rich synaptic functions like excitatory post synaptic current (EPSC), paired pulse facilitation (PPF), short and long-term potentiation (STP/LTP) or depression (STD/LTD) and spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP) [20]. Switching energies can reach the tens-of-femtojoule regime per synaptic event, placing them among the lowest ones reported so far with novel neuromorphic devices. Additionally, the ferroelectric properties of the devices stayed satisfactory even under bending (7 mm radius of bending) or over 500 bending cycles [45]. In P(VDF-TrFE) based FTJ devices, nearly linear synaptic weight updates were achieved with 20 ns pulse width (Figure 4) that led to more than 91% accuracy in MNIST handwritten digit recognition tasks in a multilayer perceptron (MLP) based DNN. [46] However, there exists a trade-off between linearity and dynamic conductance range (DR). To get a better DR and linearity, a three-terminal transistor has proven to be a better alternative.

2.1.2.2 | Ferroelectric-FETs Synapses. In a three terminal FeFET, the ferroelectric gate insulator switches polarization to modulate an organic or inorganic channel, enabling linear,

FIGURE 4 | (a) Potentiation and depression due to incremental pulsing scheme applied on an MFS FTJ memristor showing large DR, analog state linearity and symmetry can be achieved in these devices using these pulse schemes. (b) The same device potentiation and depression under identical pulsing scheme with 0.8 V pulses showing limited DR and nonlinear weight update. (c) FTJs showing symmetric STDP under ultrafast operation (in ns range) (d) improvement in conductance update linearity using less crystalline molecular ferroelectric film together with 20 ns width write pulse. Using improved conductance linearity, (e) a DNN accelerator simulated using FTJ synapses could identify (f) MNIST 28x28 handwritten digits with more than 91% accuracy. (a–c) Reproduced under the terms of CC-BY license from [22], (d) from [44] and (e, f) from [46].

incremental potentiation and depression and low-voltage operation [47, 48]. Earlier in P(VDF-TrFE)-based FeFETs, a large operating voltage ~ 20 V was needed as thinning down the ferroelectric layer resulted in large gate leakage. In recent times, use of composite ferroelectric/dielectric stack allowed FE layer thinning that allowed lowering operating voltage < 4 V and improving weight update linearity [41]. Utilizing these hybrid gate stacks, MLP based DNNs achieved $\sim 96\%$ accuracy in MNIST-classification simulated from measured device characteristics. Coupling P(VDF-TrFE) with MoS₂ or black phosphorus channels yields steep, nonvolatile gating and neuromorphic behaviors (LTP/LTD, STDP) while leveraging high mobility of 2D channels. Mono- or few atomic layer semiconductors also allow extreme mechanical flexibility of the devices [49].

2.1.2.3 | Ferroelectric Neurons. Utilizing the ferroelectric depolarizing field, FTJs or FeFETs can also be used as memristive neuron devices that can replicate biological neuronal switching dynamics. Lowering the thickness of ferroelectric films or poor screening of polarization charges at the ferro-electrode interface, introduced by low-doped semiconductors [23] or introduction of a dielectric layer at the interface [41] results in the higher depolarization field leading to faster decay of polarization states. Using this principle, single device neurons have been designed without the need of additional resistors or capacitors in the circuit that showed both oscillatory and LIF neuronal dynamics [23]. Switching frequency of the oscillatory neurons or integration and leak time of the LIF neurons can be designed by engineering the stack [23, 41] or designing proper pulsing protocol [23].

2.1.3 | Near and In-Sensor Computing With Ferroelectric Components

In biological systems, sensing and computing take place in physically close locations like in the sensory organs. Human eye or skin, for instance, not only work as a sensor but also involve data encoding, compression, adaptation and other complex computations. To make intelligent systems more biology-like, it is important to design systems with near or in-sensor computing. Some recent advances in the fields of neuromorphic vision and touch, based on flexible ferroelectric devices, are discussed in the following sections.

2.1.3.1 | Opto-Ferroelectric Synapses for In-Sensor Computing. Optoelectronic ferroelectric synapses co-locate sensing, memory, and computing, reducing data movement and latency for event-driven vision like retinal filtering and motion detection [50]. By incorporating light-sensitive semiconductor channels, like organic, metal oxides or 2D semiconductors with ferroelectric gating, devices achieve simultaneous sensing, memory, and computation, a key for vision front ends. Results show visual-perception tasks like retinal pre-processing, dynamic vision, photopic adaptation etc. functions implemented directly in ferroelectric synapses [50, 51]. Liu et al. reported a ferroelectric α -In₂Se₃ optoelectronic synapse with dynamic temporal response. A ferroelectric α -In₂Se₃ optoelectronic synapse with dynamic temporal response was reported by Liu et al. A reservoir physically built using α -In₂Se₃ synapses has been used in a mixed-signal, multimodal reservoir computing system designed for numerical and fast response code detection. The

FIGURE 5 | (a) Diagrammatic representation of the human vision functionality demonstrating the retina's visual adaptation and the visual cortex's ability to identify and extract features from the optical data the retina perceives. (b) A full neuromorphic vision sensor made up of a neuromorphic convolutional neural network (CNN) based on basic 2D-FeFETs and retinomorph image sensors. The FeFET exhibits a nonlinear photoresponse for a retina-like visual adaptation function and, concurrently, a linearly programmable long-term plasticity for neuromorphic computing due to the electro/photo-induced ferroelectric reversal and the entangled ferroelectricity-semiconductor property of the channel material α - In_2Se_3 . (c) A schematic illustrating the functionality of a crossbar array hardware for both (d) the image detection and recognition process for a handwritten digit "3." (a,b) Reproduced with permission [53]. (c,d) Reproduced with permission [54]. Copyright 2020, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

system may fuse many sensors and has adjustable dynamics [52].

In a 2D ferroelectric semiconductor-based transistor, retinomorph image sensing concept is demonstrated, as shown in Figure 5a,b [53]. By using the entangled ferroelectric-semiconductor property of α - In_2Se_3 channel and electro/photo-induced ferroelectric polarization reversal, the devices demonstrated both a linearly programmable long-term plasticity for neuromorphic computing and a nonlinear photoresponse that mimicked the visual adaptation behavior of the retina. Because of the channel's suitable bandgap of 1.38 eV, the visual adaptation is visible throughout a wide wavelength range, from deep-ultraviolet (275 nm) to near-infrared (808 nm). Furthermore, the devices demonstrate a wide dynamic range of up to 20.3 stops in a matter of minutes, which is significantly greater than what the human retina can accomplish in the same amount of adaption time. This study combined 3×3 sensor arrays with a software-simulated convolutional neural network (CNN) to experimentally demonstrate the visual adaption behavior on broadband-dim-image binary classification tasks. The system demonstrated a high recognition accuracy of 93.0% with good

linearity and repeatability in the weights programming in the transistors, which is 20% greater than that of an incomplete system without the front-end retinomorph sensors. Using a 2D MoS_2 -based transistor array, high-level digital image recognition task was successfully shown using a simulated CNN [54]. One important finding of this work is that the optical encoding method is far more difficult and time-consuming than the image capturing process. The overall speed of image processing may be slowed down as a result. Furthermore, the hardware's ability to recognize images is limited by the necessity for offline training to produce the necessary conductance values, which is challenging to extend to big data settings. To increase the overall system-level performance, faster encoding and more intelligent training techniques are required.

Using organic ferroelectric-dielectric hybrid gate stack and organic semiconductor dioctylbenzothienobenzothiophene (C8-BTBT) based neuristor, self-adaptation functions of the biological retina is demonstrated [55]. The device couples the optically-controlled ferroelectric polarization reversal with the trap-induced effects allowing autonomous modulation of the photosensitivity in time according to light intensities. The

dynamic adaptive behavior, similar to biological scotopic and photopic adaptations, allowed these devices to process visual information with pJ-level energy consumption under various light conditions with image pre-processing improving the image recognition accuracy.

Using a reconfigurable 2D WSe₂/P(VDF-TrFE) neuromorphic vision sensor, high-precision programmability is demonstrated using progressive ferroelectric polarization. The devices enable emergence of self-powered bidirectional photocurrents over 6 bits and a uniform step of 6 pA. The photocurrents show nonvolatility, symmetry, reversibility, and high linearity that allows efficient motion detection by solely collecting information from the moving object. Similar to the ganglion cells in the human retina, the devices can minimize redundant data through the bidirectional photocurrent states. Using the devices, a simulated ANN could recognize motion information with an accuracy of 96.8%. Such systems with simultaneous optical signal sensing, multistate memorization, and power-efficient modulation capabilities hold promises for neuromorphic and bionic vision. A proof-of-concept 3 × 3 sensor array is demonstrated in hardware, however for application in larger systems large scale integration strategies would be needed [56].

Using 2D ferroelectric devices that emulate neuronal model functions, synaptic weights, and neural networks for image processing have also been demonstrated. As an emerging device concept, 2D ferroelectric can reach up to the sensor-memory and in-sensor computing field, approaching extremely scaled, and ultra-low power consuming devices for intelligence everywhere [57].

2.1.3.2 | Neuromorphic Touch Sensing with Ferroelectric Synapses. Human skin-inspired neuromorphic sensing and computing is about to revolutionize machine perception. Human skin is an extraordinary organ, that can detect a range of stimuli with high sensitivity and adaptability, for example, our hands can manipulate tiny objects while simultaneously understanding their texture, temperature and firmness and how much pressure it needs to hold it with. Can robots ever perceive things with the same precision and sensitivity? To emulate skin-like complex functions, neuromorphic touch sensors need to be engineered with flexible or stretchable materials to sense pressure, temperature, texture, and other physical or chemical factors integrated with neuromorphic systems that will process sensory information efficiently. Such combined sensing and computing systems can enable real-time, context-aware responses enabling adaptive systems and intelligent for healthcare, robotics, and wearables [58].

Piezoelectric PVDF-based sensors showed excellent performance in identifying different stimuli with precision and scalability [59]. By using a patterned structure that mimics the human skin, PVDF sensor could generate both piezoelectric and piezoresistive responses leading to both static and dynamic touch, temperature and vibration sensing [60]. Using MXene-based piezoresistive pressure sensors, Tan et al. [61] showed a tactile sensing coupled with synaptic photomemristor-based circuits that could mimic human afferent nerves. Neural coding allowed these spiking nerves to identify object movement, braille, and Morse code in addition to simultaneous pressure inputs. Additionally, the

system could identify and learn handwritten words and alphabets using dimensionality-reduced feature extraction and learning.

A complete hardware demonstration of a neuromorphic sensing and computation device was reported in a recent work (Figure 6). The system included a memristive system on a chip (SoC), an event-triggered pre-processing circuit, and a flexible piezoelectric haptic sensor array composed of prepoled PVDF-based 4 × 4 capacitors. The sensor pixels' transient voltage spikes are converted into decaying voltage waveforms by the pre-processing circuitry. These waveforms produced a time surface for the chip's event-based analogue IMC. When patterns were directly inscribed on the sensor array, the system's recognition accuracy ranged from 87% to 92%, and in inference tasks, the energy-delay product was about 17 times lower than on traditional digital solutions. This device demonstrates the memristive SoC's suitability for low-power, intelligent sensing technologies along with low-latency edge processing of analogue sensor data [62].

2.1.4 | Challenges and Outlook with Ferroelectric Materials

Although individual ferroelectric synaptic device performance shows essential synaptic properties, like LTP, LTD, PPF, PPD, STDP, or LIF type neuronal switching, large scale implementations of these devices have remained far from reality due to some practical challenges. For large scale system integration, issues like device yield, performance uniformity, reliability and their integration-related issues need to be addressed. From ferroelectric device side, some parameters need improvement and some need better reliability controls: (1) Large operating voltage needs to be reduced for edge applications. (2) Parameters, such as weight-update linearity, symmetry, and device-to-device spread remain the chief algorithmic pain points. (3) Ionic contributions and interfacial traps in polymer stacks lead to limited endurance. Composite dielectric-ferroelectric stack and pulse-engineering options might be helpful in this respect. (4) Imprint, fatigue, and depolarization fields in ferroelectric materials are critical issues. Minimizing imprint and maintaining stable intermediate polarization states under repeated cycling and thermal stress is essential, something which requires electrode, stack and interface optimization. In oxides, superlattice structures with mixed ferro and antiferroelectric ordering has solved this problem significantly. This can be tested for molecular ferroelectric as well. (5) Scaling and leakage: Very thin polymer films face risks like high tunneling and leakage currents due to pinholes, grain boundary and trap-assisted tunneling, while thicker films raise switching voltage and energy. Stack engineering with ALD-grown dielectric oxide can provide solutions there. (6) Array-level integration: Crossbar sneak current paths, selector compatibility, write-verify schemes, and per-synapse calibration remain open engineering problems for large, uniform arrays on flexible substrates. (7) Reliability in real environments like moisture or solvent uptake and mechanical stress cycling can perturb polarization and interfaces; encapsulation and engineered polymer blends can provide improvements. Oxide or polymer-ferroelectric synapses already deliver compelling key performance figures like femto-Joule (fJ)-level energy consumption per update, more than 10⁸-cycle endurance, flexible operation, and in-sensor functions,

FIGURE 6 | A comparison between a traditional frame-based digital sensing system and an event-based sensing system and its implementation based on a piezoelectric haptic sensor array and a memristive system on a chip (SoC) (a) Piezoelectric sensor array generates discrete spike signals upon detecting dynamic change in pressure (press and release). (b) Data acquisition and digitization in a conventional frame-based digital sensing system. The analog output of the sensors is amplified before being converted by the ADC array into digital signals. (c) Computing in digital platforms, where signals are stored in memory and processed by the CPU. (d) Event-triggered circuitry, where the circuit converts the spikes from the sensor array into decaying waveforms, which are then used to construct time surfaces containing temporal-spatial information. (e) The memristive SoC comprising of ten VMM computing cores, one RISC-V CPU, and essential peripheral digital circuits. The lower panel shows the images of the three main modules of the neuromorphic near-sensor computing system. Reproduced under the terms of CC-BY license from [62] Copyright 2026, The Author(s), under exclusive license to Springer Nature Limited.

while retaining a manufacturing pathway aligned with printing and large-area electronics. The next leaps will likely come from (i) low power array-level operation; (ii) defect-tolerant composites and interlayers that stabilize intermediate polarization; (ii) standardized pulse protocols and closed-loop write-verify for linear analog weights; (iii) co-design with algorithms that tolerate device stochasticity; and (iv) heterogeneous stacks pairing P(VDF-TrFE) with 2D or oxide semiconductor channels for stable, low-noise operation. With these advances, low thermal budget ferroelectric devices can move from only elegant device physics to robust, application-grade neuromorphic subsystems in flexible wearables and vision front ends.

For circuit and system-level implementations, more than 98% yield, performance uniformity and reliability, together with high endurance, stable polarization retention and controllable analog conductance states are essential. Improving yield and reliability at scaled nodes, therefore, needs special attention. When it comes to peripheral circuit overhead, the requirements for ferroelectric memories are different from traditional SRAM/DRAM/Flash designs. FeRAMs have destructive read-out that require immediate rewrite, whereas FeFETs and FTJs offer non-destructive current-based read operations, enabling simpler and more energy-efficient sensing circuitry. Neverthe-

less, their lower technological maturity introduces challenges in yield, variability, and endurance, motivating ongoing device- and circuit-level optimization efforts. Finally, for large data handling architectures needing very densely integrated memories and multi-layered stacked logic-memory integrations, traditional electronics would perhaps still remain the most feasible solution, however, for unconventional in-sensor computing platforms, for instance, intelligent e-skins or flexible machine vision, where memory elements can be as big as the sensor pixels, dense integration of memory is not a requirement and soft material based systems can definitely become an interesting choice.

2.2 | Organic Materials for Neuromorphic Applications

Organic materials' biocompatibility, light weight, flexibility, and tunability have led to them showing promising performance in neuromorphic applications.

Since the discovery of conductive polymers in the 1970s, [63] the field of organic electronics has advanced rapidly. Organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs), organic photovoltaics (OPVs), and organic thin-film transistors (OFETs) have achieved remarkable

success and significantly impacted modern life [64, 65]. Recently, neuro-inspired applications, such as artificial synapses and neurons, have attracted growing interest to meet the demands of neuromorphic computing in soft and wearable platforms. This is largely due to the intrinsic biocompatibility of organic materials and their responsiveness to analytes in biological media [66–70]. Additionally, organic devices exhibit high switching ratios, [71] low operating voltages [72] and compatibility with integration onto flexible substrates [73, 74]. For example, biomemristors with high ON/OFF ratios, based on nanocomposite films of carbon quantum dots dispersed in chitosan, a natural polymer electrolyte, have been fabricated with coplanar nanogap metal electrodes [75]. These nanogap asymmetric electrodes structures have been proven to be ideal platforms to host nanomaterials, especially when a low-cost, wafer scalable nanopatterning technique, namely adhesion lithography, is used for their fabrication [76]. On another instance, carbon nanotubes were blended in a polyfluorene polymer solution and spin-coated on coplanar nanogap electrodes to form devices that exhibited multiple memory states [77].

A wide range of organic memory and neuromorphic device structures have been reported, with three main types dominating research literature: metal-insulator-metal (MIM) resistive switching devices and two types of transistors: organic field effect transistors (OFET) and organic electrochemical transistors (OECT). MIM devices with organic insulators are among the simplest and earliest reported resistive/memory switching devices. Gregor's work in 1968 [78] demonstrated resistive switching in devices with 10–25 nm organic insulation sandwiched between two Pd electrodes. The resistance change obtained with these devices reached many orders of magnitude at 1–2 V, with a switching time of 1 μ s, retention time of 30 min, and cycling endurance of 250 000 cycles. Switching behavior was also observed in other polymers, such as polystyrene and polyacetylene, [79, 80] though electrode damage was observed after switching.

MIM structures have been used to incorporate small organic molecules. For example, when a 600 nm tetracene film was deposited between gold and aluminum electrodes, it showed resistance switching up to five orders of magnitude at 4–8 V [81]. In the past two decades, novel organic materials have introduced diverse switching behaviors driven by mechanisms such as charge transfer in donor-acceptor molecules, charge trapping/detrapping in host matrices, and filament formation. An example is copper tetracyanoquinodimethane (CuTCNQ), [82] where Raman spectroscopy confirmed that when an electric field is applied, TCNQ anions that are mostly present in the high-resistance state are giving their place to neutral TCNQ molecules, bringing the device to the low-resistance state.

Two-terminal devices are particularly attractive to be employed in RRAMs. While inorganic RRAM offers high endurance, fast switching, and high storage density, [83–85] organic RRAM faces challenges, such as high-power consumption, poor stability, and dispersed voltage/resistance distributions [86]. Although basic synaptic functions, such as LTP, STP, STDP and spike-rate-dependent plasticity (SRDP) have been demonstrated, [87, 88], large-scale integration remains limited. Simple MIM structure organic devices have also been used to fabricate CNNs for image recognition applications [89].

Compared to two-terminal devices, three-terminal devices (OFETs and OECTs) are more widely reported for neuromorphic applications because they offer more controllable inputs and measurable outputs, better mimicking neurons and synapses. OFETs were first reported by Koezuka et al. in 1987, [90] using polythiophene as the channel material. Since then, OFETs have become fundamental building blocks in organic electronics, [91, 92] analogous to MOSFETs in modern electronics. In OFETs, gate voltage induces charge accumulation at the insulator/semiconductor interface, enabling doping and de-doping through the field effect [93].

OECTs, developed by Wrighton et al. in the 1980s, [94] consist of an organic semiconductor film immersed in an electrolyte. Gate voltage controls ion injection from the electrolyte into the film, modulating conductivity via doping changes. A related device, the electrolyte-gated OFET (EGOFET), resembles OECTs but relies on ionic charge layers at the channel interface without ion penetration, resulting in high capacitance due to the short charge separation distance [95].

Beyond electrical modulation, photoresponsive channel materials enable light-controlled conductivity, while mechanical force can also modulate channel properties. Combining these mechanisms with gate control enhances efficiency and expands applications to biosensing [96]. Recent advances include organic synaptic transistors demonstrating diverse plasticity and artificial sensory neurons responding to stimuli, such as light [97–99] and pressure [100–102]. Organic transistor-based artificial neural networks (ANNs) have also shown potential in pattern recognition, natural language processing (NLP), and other computational tasks [103–106]. For example, Kim et al. developed an OECT with improved memory endurance via iterative spiking neural network (SNN) learning, achieving 88.9% speech recognition accuracy [107]. Flexible organic transistors integrated with biosensing capabilities enable biochemical-mediated neuromorphic devices for intelligent biointerfaces [73, 108–111]. OECTs offer advantages over OFETs in these applications, including lower operating voltages (<1 V) and ion-driven conduction that mimics biological synapses [112, 113].

OFETs and OECTs require high charge mobility, while OECTs also demand ion permeability. Common materials include polymer poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) doped with poly(styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) [114, 115] and poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (P3HT), [96, 116] alongside various small molecules and conjugated polymers (see Table 1). Both device types can be fabricated on flexible substrates for applications in electronic skin, wearables, food safety, environmental monitoring, healthcare, and edge computing [117]. Flexibility can be achieved through intrinsically stretchable materials or structural design. For example, Dai et al. used poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) substrates and thienothiophene (TT)-2,2'-bithiophene (BT) copolymer with triethylene glycol (TEG) side chains, known as p(g2T-T), channels to achieve >200% tensile capacity and 5000 cycles of durability [118].

Large-scale circuits require high device yield and stability. Zabihipour et al. reported that achieving 50% functional yield in 100-OECT circuits demands >99.3% yield per device, posing significant manufacturing challenges [119]. Wang et al. developed

TABLE 1 | Summary of representative organic neuromorphic devices.

Device type	Active material(s)	Neuromorphic function(s)	Application	Flexibility
MIM	bis-4-(N-carbazolyl)phenyl)phenylphosphine oxide (BCPO) [84]	SRDP, STDP	Synaptic application	no
	azulene-based 2D conjugated covalent organic framework (COF-Azu) [86]	LTP	Image recognition (simulated)	no
	poly(1,3,5-trivinyl-1,3,5-trimethyl cyclotrisiloxane) (pV3D3) [123]	LTP, STP	Face classification (simulated)	yes
	parylene [124]	STDP	STDP-like learning	no
OFET	poly(ethylene furanoate) (PEF) [125]	LTP	Resistive switching memory	yes
	Pentacene/Au NP [126]	STP, SRDP	Synapse in neuromorphic circuit	no
	poly[[4,8-bis[5-(2-ethylhexyl)-2-thienyl]-benzo[1,2- <i>b</i> :4,5- <i>b'</i>]dithiophene-2,6-diyl][2-(2-ethyl-1-oxohexyl)-thieno[3,4- <i>b</i>]thiophenediyl]] (PBDTTT-C-T) with P(VDF-TrFE) as insulator [127]	LTP, SDDP	Light and dopamine detector	no
	poly{2,2'-[(2,5-bis(2-hexyldecyl)-3,6-dioxo-2,3,5,6-tetrahydropyrrolo[3,4- <i>c</i>]pyrrole-1,4-diyl)dithiophene]-5,5'-diyl-alt-thiophen-2,5-diyl} (PDPP3T):[6,6]-phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) (photoactive layer) and P3HT:PCBM (floating gate) [96]	Light intensity photoadaptation	Adaptive light sensor	no
	P3HT/P(VDF-TrFE) (ferroelectric)/PEDOT:PSS (gate) [114]	LTP	Pressure/tactile, electronic skin	yes
	naphthalene diimide and polyamide derivative (<i>p</i> -NDI) [105]	SRDP	Reservoir and in-sensor computing	yes
	poly(2-(3,3'-bis(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)-[2,2'-bithiophen]-5-yl)thieno[3,2- <i>b</i>]thiophene) [p(g2T-TT)] [128]	LTP	ECG pattern classification vector-matrix multiplication	yes
OECT	Pentance [73]	Spiking generation	Artificial afferent nerve	yes
	P3HT [129]	LTP, STP	Neural network (simulated)	no
	PEDOT:PSS [70]	STP	Synaptic application	no
	P3HT:PCBM [130]	STP, LTP	Facial recognition (simulated)	no

Abbreviations: LTP: long-term plasticity, SDDP: spike-duration-dependent plasticity, SRDP: spike-rate-dependent plasticity, STDP: spike-timing-dependent plasticity, STP: short-term plasticity.

a multimodal sensor for real-time cardiac diagnosis using a 156×5 cv-OECT-based ANN, integrating sensing, memory, and processing, while leveraging reservoir computing (RC) to reduce training resource requirements [104].

2.2.1 | Challenges and Outlook with Organic Materials

Key challenges for organic neuromorphic devices include optimizing active materials in terms of both their electrical and mechanical properties, exploring new device configurations, such as the nanogap coplanar electrode 2-terminal architecture, and addressing integration issues with silicon-based technologies.

Solution processability is an important advantage offered by organic materials for low-cost fabrication routes compatible with flexible substrates. Nevertheless, it also poses challenges when it comes to standard photolithography patterning of micrometer-long features due to solubility issues presented by the active materials with the organic solvents used during photolithography process steps, ultimately resulting in large cell areas (e.g., as defined by printing or shadow masking techniques). Novel fabrication processes, such as the initiated chemical vapor deposition (iCVD) process (Figure 7a), adhesion lithography and advanced printing techniques, must be further developed to reduce device-to-device variability and ensure compatibility with microelectronics [120]. Large-scale array-level demonstration

FIGURE 7 | (a) (left) A schematic of a flexible pV3D3 8×8 electronic synapse array with memristor structure Cu (top electrode: presynaptic neuron)/pV3D3/Al (bottom electrode: postsynaptic neuron) fabricated with ICVD polymerization on a flexible poly(ether sulfone) (PES) substrate. (right) Cross sectional TEM image of the flexible 20-nm thin pV3D3 film comprising the memristor. Reproduced with permission. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society [123]. (b) A screen-printed sheet containing 760 OEETs, with a zoomed-in section of one OEET, and a cross sectional drawing of the different layers of the OEET structure. Reproduced under the terms of CC BY 4.0 license. Copyright 2020, Springer Nature [119]. (c) An artificial and a biological afferent nerve system shown together for comparison of their components. The artificial one consists of pressure sensors, an organic ring oscillator (OFET) and a synaptic transistor (OEET), which are analogous to receptor, nerve fiber and synapse, respectively. Reproduced from Kim et al., *Science*, 10.1126/science.aao0098 [2018], *AAAS* [73]. (d) Photograph of wearable reservoir computing (RC) system based on p-NDI phototransistor (structure also shown). To the left, the process of image learning and forgetting of the letter 'F' through optical stimulation as well as the process of image contrast enhancement after training are also depicted. Reproduced under the terms of CC BY 4.0 license. Copyright 2023, Springer Nature [105].

remains scarce with most integration research is still conducted via simulation [121, 122]. However, some large-scale demonstrations have been shown, for instance in Figure 7b, where an example of an A4 PET sheet comprising 760 OEETs is shown. Moreover, the ability to tune the properties of organic materials via tailored chemical design, offers extra functionalities that can be leveraged to emulate both the sensing mechanisms of afferent nerves in addition to signal (information) processing. These systems combined with efferent (motor) nerves can be extremely useful in neurobotics and neuroprosthetics. An example of such a hybrid system is presented in Figure 7c, where resistive pressure sensors (tactile receptors) collect the sensing information, organic ring oscillators (nerve fibers) convert it into voltage action potentials, which are integrated with a synaptic transistor to a postsynaptic current fed to motor nerves to actuate muscles [73]. In order to achieve effective bio-interfacing, the performance metrics of these artificial afferent systems must be fine-tuned to match those of the biological efferent ones (motor nerves) (e.g., the sensitivity and working range of the pressure sensors, oscillating frequency of ring oscillators around 0–100 Hz, close to zero power consumption at rest, temporal dynamics of the transistor with decay times of 1.5–5 msec, etc.).

Taking this multifunctionality provided by organic materials design one step further, artificial general intelligence systems may be devised, e.g. photonic neuromorphic systems that can extend the retinal prosthetics capabilities beyond the human perceived optical spectrum (bionic eye). Material-algorithm co-design has proven to be critical in such applications. A dynamic in-sensor Reservoir-Computing (RC) system based on wearable organic transistor was paired with memristive organic ionic gel diode as a read-out and demonstrated very good performance separability, fading memory, and echo state property when subjected to various tasks (Figure 7d). This was attributed to the spatiotemporal dynamics of RC that enables extraction of features from event-based videos. This organic materials-algorithmic approach co-design resulted in significantly reduced training cost, compared with that of conventional deep-learning models, as in the long-term organic memory, the learning of the RC is limited to the readout layer.

Table 1 summarizes key neuromorphic functions demonstrated with several organic materials employed in MIM, OFET or OEET devices and their respective application area, with a note also of their flexibility assessment.

2.3 | 2D Materials for Flexible Neuromorphic Devices

2.3.1 | 2D Flexible Neuromorphic Devices

Two-dimensional (2D) materials are now recognized as outstanding foundational components for the development of advanced neuromorphic hardware. Their atomically thin structure, large surface area, high carrier mobility, tunable bandgaps, and ultralow switching energy [131] make them ideal for neuromorphic computing devices. Moreover, the excellent conductance tunability of 2D materials enables precise control over analog synaptic weight updates, which is essential for mimicking short- and long-term plasticity in artificial neural networks [132].

Flexible neuromorphic devices are engineered to replicate the functions of biological neural networks, while being able to bend, stretch, or conform to different shapes. This makes them ideal for applications like wearable electronics [132] and soft robotics, [133, 134] where conformability and mechanical flexibility are important. The choice of substrate material is essential for developing flexible neuromorphic devices and commonly used substrate materials based on specific requirements are polyimide (PI) [135] for thermal resistance, poly(dimethyl siloxane) (PDMS) [136] and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) [137] for light transmission, polyurethane (PU) [138] for stretchability, and paper [139] for biocompatibility. The 2D materials used in these devices can be classified into three different classes: 2D semiconductors, such as transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs), [140, 141] black phosphorus (BP), [142] 2D perovskites, [143] 2D dielectric materials, commonly hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN), [144] and 2D conductive materials, like MXenes, [145] and graphene. [146].

Inherent properties like high Young's modulus, breaking strength, and mechanical flexibility make 2D materials, ideal for use on flexible substrates [147]. TMDCs have a layered structure, where transition metal atoms (such as Mo, W, Hf, V, Ti) are situated directly between two layers of chalcogen atoms (S, Se, or Te). The strong covalent bonds within these layers give TMDCs an exceptional in-plane mechanical strength and a high Young's modulus, typically ranging from 120 to 400 GPa, with breaking strains between 6 and 11% [148–150]. Also, tungsten based TMDCs (WX_2) are stronger than molybdenum based (MoX_2) and sulfides are generally stronger than selenides and tellurides [151, 152]. Graphene is highly flexible, has low stiffness, an exceptionally large Young's modulus of about 1 TPa, and can stretch up to around 25 % strain without breaking [153, 154]. BP exhibits a Young's modulus ranging from 44 to 166 GPa, alongside a fracture strain of 30% in its monolayer form and 32% in multilayer configurations [155]. The flexible neuromorphic devices should possess key properties, such as flexibility, stretchability and stability [146]. Flexibility shows the ability of the material to withstand bending, and stretchability to endure elongation and strain without breaking. The bending radius and strain ratio are used for evaluating these properties. Stability allows the material to tolerate repeated bending and stretching without performance loss. To use these flexible devices for wearable technology and health care, the material should

also be biocompatible, namely, able to interface with living tissue without adverse effects, and biodegradable, meaning it can safely break down into smaller, non-toxic components [146].

The weak van der Waals (vdW) bonding between individual 2D layers allows diverse materials to be stacked into multifunctional heterostructures that combine electronic, ionic, and optoelectronic functions within a single device, such as the quantum start effect, optical harmonic generation, and second and third order optical nonlinearities [156, 157]. The electronic properties of van der Waals heterostructure can be fine-tuned to control the properties, such as ferroelectricity, [158] piezoelectricity, [159, 160] carrier mobility, [161] and contact resistance [162] through various engineering methods, including stacking sequence, twist angle, applied electric fields, and interface engineering [163]. These heterostructures enable new device functionalities and support monolithic three-dimensional (M3D) integration, allowing dense vertical stacking of active components to mimic the complex connectivity and parallelism of biological neural tissue [157]. Moreover, 2D materials can be compatible with scalable, large-area fabrication techniques, such as transfer printing, [164] inkjet printing, [164] atomic layer deposition (ALD), [166] and chemical vapor deposition (CVD), [165] which enables a new class of intelligent and adaptive technologies from wearable health monitors, [167] soft robotics, [168] and neuromorphic skins for real-time, on-body intelligence [169].

Depending on the device architecture, flexible neuromorphic devices can be classified as two-terminal (2T) memristive devices and three-terminal (3T) transistor-type synaptic devices. The unique combination of mechanical flexibility, electrical tunability, and ability to form multifunctional heterostructures makes 2D materials highly promising for next-generation neuromorphic systems. The following sections explore recent progress in both 2T and 3T flexible neuromorphic devices using 2D materials, focusing on their working mechanisms, performance, and remaining challenges.

2.3.2 | 2D Material-Based Flexible Memristive Synaptic Devices

Memristive devices are usually 2T devices built in a metal-insulator-metal (MIM) structure with the insulator being the active layer [170]. Upon the application of an electric field, the memristor resistance changes due to physical or chemical reconfiguration in the active layer, which manifests as either a digital or analog resistive switching at the device level. Flexible memristive devices made from 2D semiconductors mimic the brain's ability to process information efficiently, enabling flexible, bio-compatible, and mechanically robust systems. The imperfections in 2D materials, such as grain boundaries, vacancies, dopants, phase boundaries, facilitate resistive switching behavior in 2D memristive devices [166]. These neuromorphic devices maintain stable performance under deformation, while delivering energy-efficient analog weight updates critical to artificial neural networks [171, 172]. These devices can emulate key synaptic behaviors, including potentiation/depression, STDP, and

short-term/long-term memory transitions, thereby closely mimicking biological learning processes.

The main resistive switching mechanisms in 2D memristors are defect migration, charge trapping/de-trapping and ion transport [173]. Depending on the active layer composition and device architecture, 2D material-based memristors can exhibit either unipolar or bipolar resistive switching. Unipolar switching typically arises from Joule heating-assisted filament formation, while bipolar switching results from field-driven ionic migration or charge modulation. Furthermore, these devices may demonstrate digital or analog characteristics, where the latter is fundamental for implementing synaptic plasticity in artificial neural networks.

In TMDCs like MoS₂ and WS₂, the sulfur vacancies are the primary defects causing resistive switching [173–175]. An applied electric field, force these vacancies to migrate through the 2D lattice, modulating the Schottky barrier at the metal-semiconductor interface or creating localized conductive channels. The weak covalent bonding between chalcogen atoms and transition metals facilitates low-energy vacancy formation, enabling low switching voltages. Another mechanism involves the charge trapping/de-trapping, which occurs due to the traps at interfaces or within the 2D layer (via engineered defects or heterostructures), providing a means to modulate carrier injection and enabling analog weight updates and multilevel memory states [174]. In some 2D memristive devices, the ion transport mechanism occurs due to the migration of ionic species (e.g., oxygen ions or other mobile defects), which form or rupture a local conductive filament, enabling resistive switching [175].

The recent advances in TMDC materials have extensive applications in flexible neuromorphic devices [176–178]. For example, wafer-scale MoS₂ memristor arrays fabricated via solution-processing have shown excellent endurance (1×10^7 switching cycles), low set/reset voltage (0.65 V/−0.9 V), analog switching performance, linear weight updates, and >98% recognition accuracy on the MNIST dataset, highlighting their scalability and reliability for neuromorphic learning. The switching characteristics are controlled by the diffusion of inter-flake sulfur vacancies, and this transfer-free processing of 2D layers at room temperature is ideal for integrating onto low melting point flexible substrates [140]. Similarly, low-temperature (250°C) plasma-assisted CVD-grown MoS₂ on flexible polyimide (PI) substrates achieved high ON/OFF ratios ($\sim 10^5$), long retention ($> 2 \times 10^5$ s), with an ON/OFF resistive switching ratio of $\sim 10^3$ stable after 800 bending cycles, enabling the fabrication of large-area crossbar memristor arrays without any transfer process [135]. Ion-intercalated MoS₂ neuromorphic devices made by sputtering onto PDMS substrates utilize ion movement along grain boundaries to achieve robust analog plasticity and mechanical durability, displaying a high ON/OFF ratio of about $\sim 10^5$ [141]. In addition, MoTe₂ strain-sensitive memristor that integrates sensing and storage, demonstrated stable retention and switching stability for wearable artificial intelligence skin applications [179]. Likewise, solution-processed WS₂ thin films have been successfully used as the resistive switching layer in flexible RRAM devices, exhibiting minimal operating voltages, substantial ON/OFF current ratios,

and prolonged retention capabilities, while maintaining stable performance under mechanical bending [180].

Wang et al. demonstrated heterostructure-based neuromorphic fibers, such as Ag/MoS₂/HfAlO_x/CNT systems, that integrate both synaptic and neuronal behaviors within a reconfigurable network, achieving ultra-low energy consumption (~ 1.9 fJ/spike), as shown in Figure 8a–c [132]. These reconfigurable fiber networks have been woven into intelligent textiles capable of adaptive thermal control and self-learning, demonstrating a pathway toward bioinspired neuromorphic fabrics that combine computation, sensing, and actuation.

Boron nitride (BN), a 2D dielectric material with a dielectric constant of about 3 and a wide bandgap of 5.97 eV, is emerging as a promising resistive switching layer. In 2021, Meng et al. reported a flexible boron nitride based memristive device with TaN/BN/ITO structure, which combines both digital logic-in-memory and analog neuromorphic computing functions in a single device. Due to the superior mechanical robustness of BN, it maintains stable potentiation and depression behavior under repeated bending at various radii, as shown in Figure 8d,e. It performs Boolean logic operations and exhibits ultra-low power consumption of around 198 fJ per spike and ultrafast synaptic response in the order of 1 μ s [144]. Additionally, carbon-doped hBN (C–hBN) memristors show promising vacancy-mediated resistive switching allowing for low operating voltages (<1 V), substantial ON/OFF ratios ($> 10^5$), fast switching speeds under 240 ns, and excellent retention (10^4 s at 120°C) [137]. Moreover, the C–hBN devices maintain reliable operation on flexible PI and PET substrates even after 500 bending cycles, highlighting their promise for ultra-scaled, thermally stable, and flexible non-volatile memory and neuromorphic electronics [137].

MXenes, a family of conductive 2D carbides and nitrides M_{n+1}X_nT_x, exhibit tunable electrical properties. MXene-based devices often struggle with stability, retention, and endurance required for neural networks and these challenges are partially addressed through surface modification, [181, 182] partial oxidation, [183–185] ion doping [186] and polymer bending [187]. MXene hybrids with elastomers or oxides have been used for multifunctional, in-sensor neuromorphic processing that integrates sensing and computation [145, 185].

Graphene is a 2D carbon material widely used in neuromorphic [176, 188–190] sensing applications due to its superior electrical, physicochemical and mechanical properties. Graphene also faces some challenges, such as no bandgap and poor water stability, which limits its applications. Therefore, different derivatives of graphene are developed, such as graphene oxide (GO) [191, 192] and reduced graphene oxide [193].

Vertically oriented Ruddlesden–Popper (RP) 2D halide perovskite (BA₂MA₃Pb₆I₁₉) based flexible 7 × 7 crossbar ReRAM array exhibited high endurance (5×10^6 cycles), and long retention (2×10^5 s). The vertically aligned nanocrystalline channels enable stable conductive filament formation, yielding a high ON/OFF ratio ($\sim 10^7$), ultra-low voltage operation ($< \pm 0.15$ V), and remarkable moisture and bending stability over one year [143].

FIGURE 8 | Illustration of (a) a textile memristor network, (b) the fiber-based memristor structure composed of Ag/MoS₂/HfAlO_x/CNT layers, and (c) SEM images (top) alongside cross sectional TEM images (bottom) of the fiber-based memristor, (d) Diagram illustrating the device in both flat and curved states, showing reversible switching comparable to the flat configuration. (e) Long-term potentiation (LTP) and long-term depression (LTD) responses triggered by voltage pulse sequences applied to the device while flat and bent at radii of 20, 15, and 10 mm and (f) Diagram of the flexible artificial synapse array, a magnified cross sectional view of an individual device, and a photograph of the flexible, transparent device. (a–c) Reproduced under the terms of CC-BY license from [132] (d,e) Reproduced with permission from [144] (f) Reproduced under the terms of CC-BY license from [202].

2.3.3 | 2D Material-Based Flexible Synaptic Transistors

The three terminal synaptic transistors based on 2D semiconductors have emerged as a versatile framework for realizing neuromorphic systems that combine mechanical compliance with functional complexity. Unlike two-terminal memristors, these devices offer an additional degree of control via a gate electrode, which enables precise modulation of channel conductance and facilitates the simultaneous execution of sensory and synaptic task essential for brain-inspired electronics.

Field-effect transistor (FET)-based synaptic devices come in three main types: charge-trapping FETs (CT-FETs), electrolyte-gated FETs (EG-FETs), [194, 195] and ferroelectric FETs (Fe-FETs) [41, 196]. Each type works through a different physical process. CT-FETs control the flow of electrical current by trapping and releasing charges, which allows them to adjust their conductance and mimic the way synapses strengthen or weaken over time, an essential property for both short- and long-term learning. EG-FETs rely on the movement of ions within an electrolyte, [194] while Fe-FETs use changes in ferroelectric material polarization. Both EG-FETs and Fe-FETs operate at low voltages, providing stable and energy-efficient performance, making them well-suited for flexible and durable neuromorphic computing devices.

In 2020, Wang et al. developed a flexible MoS₂-based charge-trapping CT-FET with ultralow energy consumption (18.3 aJ/spike), fast operation (100 ns), excellent data storage capability, and high mechanical stability under bending (5 mm radius), capable of mimicking various synaptic behaviors and modulated by both electrical and optical inputs [197]. Tang et al. [198] demonstrated wafer-scale monolayer MoS₂ transistors and circuits using thin high- κ dielectrics and metal gates on both rigid and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substrates. These devices operate at low voltages (<1 V), show high current densities, sharp switching, negligible hysteresis, and ultra-low leakage currents. Their flexible integrated circuits maintained over 96% yield and worked reliably under bending [198]. A 2D WSe₂-based one-transistor-one-resistor (1T1R) memory cell was successfully realized through low-temperature hybrid co-integration, merging a surface-functionalized WSe₂ p-FET and a solution-processed WSe₂ resistive RAM. This approach achieves a 100× performance enhancement in the transistor, ultra-low switching energy (~2.6 pJ per bit) in the memory, and paves the way for vertically stacked, high-density 3D embedded memory systems beyond traditional silicon technology [199].

Flexible field-effect transistors (FETs) fabricated using MoS₂ with EG-FETs highlight rapid progress in electrical and mechanical reliability [200, 201]. Lee et al. demonstrated ultrathin flexible MoS₂ based electrolyte-gated thin film transistors on PI substrate, exhibit an ON/OFF ratio of ~10⁷, excellent endurance (>2.5 × 10⁴ pulses) [200]. Using hybrid organic-inorganic AlO_x electrolyte and electrical tuning, these devices reached strong classification accuracy on datasets like CIFAR-10 (90.3%) and NIH chest X-rays (81.8%) with fewer parameters than typical neural networks. The devices remained stable even after 1000 bending cycles of 3.5 mm radius [200].

Hwang et al. first demonstrated a high-density, hemispherical curved image sensor array using an ultrathin, soft MoS₂-graphene

heterostructure EG-FET. This soft, IR-blind retinal implant is mechanically compatible with tissue, offering high-resolution sensing and direct neural stimulation with minimal damage. An ultra-flexible artificial synaptic array built from a 2D MoS₂/LiSiO_x heterostructure directly fabricated on colorless polyimide, eliminating the need for complex transfer steps (see Figure 8h). The devices show excellent stability and plasticity, maintaining reliable synaptic behavior, even after 700 bending cycles or when curved to 10 mm, with strong learning performance reflected in 95% accuracy on the MNIST dataset. This work demonstrates a major step toward soft, low-power neuromorphic electronics for wearable and adaptive computing systems [202]. Ming et al. [203] developed fully 2D ambipolar FETs based on a graphene/WSe₂/h-BN/graphene van der Waals heterostructure that achieve high ON/OFF ratios exceeding 10⁸, enabling transparent, flexible CMOS-like inverters with excellent voltage gain, reconfigurable logic applications, with over 70% optical transparency and reliable performance under bending radii under 0.5 cm [203].

Besides transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs), other emerging 2D materials, such as MXenes [204] and black phosphorus (BP), [205, 206] have shown great promise for flexible and energy-efficient neuromorphic devices. However, both suffer from stability issues in ambient conditions, requiring surface functionalization or protective coatings to enhance durability. Pristine graphene exhibits ambipolar behavior, which can be affected by intrinsic defects such as vacancies, wrinkles, and grain boundaries, as well as by extrinsic doping from adsorbed ions and molecules [207, 208]. In addition, its conductivity can be effectively modulated through capacitive coupling, making graphene a promising channel material for field-effect transistors (FETs) [209, 210]. Consequently, graphene-based electrolyte-gated FETs (EG-FETs) can be employed to emulate synaptic functions [211, 212].

2.3.4 | Outlook and Challenges with 2D Materials

The key challenges with using 2D materials lie in their fabrication techniques. Specifically, their large-area uniform growth is a very active subject of research. This is clearly apparent as different applications require an array of different characteristics. For example, memristive applications on flexible substrates require a low temperature, transfer-free process with control over the defect density and switching stochasticity. On the other hand, applications with three terminal controls require high mobility transistors, with high ON/OFF ratio, and low switching voltage. These qualities are usually met by high temperature epitaxial processes that further complicate transfer of the ultrathin films. The key challenge here is closing the gap between high and low temperature fabrication, while simultaneously achieving control over the defect density, electrical performance, and stability. The current trend indicates that this will be achieved by a combination of traditional deposition processes with additional modifications, for instance by engineering lower temperature higher reactivity precursors. This caters to industry adoption by lowering entry equipment investments. A significant opportunity in this domain lies in the development of p-type materials of comparable performance. The functionality of high-performance p-type 2D semiconductors is paramount

to increasing circuit complexity (e.g. CMOS logic) and density. WSe₂ and MoTe₂ are leading that front with other emerging options such as WTe₂, GaSe, and Bi₂O₂Se following. Naturally, the choice will be decided on the integrability, compatibility, performance and robustness of the material. At the device level, contact engineering is key to tuning performance and finding the best combination of metal-semiconductor has not been a trivial subject. The gate material has also seen a boom in development, aiming at thinner more robust stacks, especially when combined with ferroelectric solutions. BN has offered key advantages by passivating defects, protecting and offering dielectric properties, however its high-quality growth directly on other materials remains a challenge, often requiring complex transfer steps that reduce yield. Beyond graphene and TMDCs, MXenes, and BP offer excellent properties, expanding their capabilities in both the electronic and photonic domains.

2D material flexible neuromorphic devices may be employed in applications, such as electronic-skin, wearable health monitors or even smart prosthetics, vision and olfactory sensors [15, 213, 214]. This utilization imposes significant demands beyond what is readily achievable in proof-of-concept devices. These systems are regularly part of mobile platforms putting constraints on energy uses, switching energies of a few pJ per event down to the fJ range in rigid-substrate equivalents, are comparable to biological synapses and help prevent thermal buildup on low-conductivity flexible substrates [215]. In addition, this requirement mitigates potential thermal build up on the low thermal conductivity substrates used in these applications. A major advantage of neuromorphic systems is that power consumption is mostly event-driven [216] 2D material devices with low static consumption achieving ON/OFF ratios of more than 6 orders of magnitude are a typical requirement for flexible applications.

High-density integration is essential for in-sensor computing and bio-interfacing, where sensing and computation must co-exist within tight spatial and functional constraints. The patterning technology is in part a limiting factor here, with 2D materials offering a major advantage over bulk semiconductors, in the form of stacking, with a natural pathway toward 3D integration [217]. This relaxes the spatial integration density, whilst reducing the spacing between computational and sensing layers. The device variability plays a paramount role in achieving a high integration density that is available to the application. Although neural networks are tolerant to a certain degree to variations, 2D materials, especially those with hard grain boundaries, such as those grown by CVD, result in significant device-to-device variations. Technologies that offer smaller uniform grains, such as with ALD, are more suitable for achieving the key 5%–10% variation for commercial adoption [218].

Bio-interfacing and sensory-feedback systems must operate below the ~10 ms human latency threshold, requiring nanosecond-scale device switching, challenging for ion-migration 2D memristors but feasible for ferroelectric devices. Conventional reliance on ADCs in flexible neuromorphic systems creates power and interconnect bottlenecks, making in-sensing, in-memory computing a far more efficient alternative.

2.4 | Multimodal Transistors as a Versatile New Tool for Analog and Mixed Signal Processing

The multimodal transistor (MMT, Figure 9a) [219] is a recently introduced transistor architecture that extends the contact-controlled transistor (CCT) operation originally demonstrated by the source-gated transistor (SGT) [220, 221]. In CCT architecture, current is governed not by channel modulation alone but by a deliberately engineered energy barrier at the source contact [222–227]. This principle contrasts with the field-effect transistor, where the gate field directly controls channel conductivity.

In the MMT, charge injection at the source and charge transport through the channel are independently regulated by two control electrodes [225]. The result is largely decoupled analog (via the source control-gate, CG1) and digital (via the channel control gate, CG2) behavior within a single structure. Because they are compatible with established thin-film processes, MMTs can be realized in a variety of oxide, organic, 2D, or silicon semiconductors that support CCT operation [222–227]. This material-agnostic nature also makes them suitable as process diagnostic elements for emerging materials and flows [228].

From an equivalent circuit perspective, the MMT functions as a voltage-controlled current source in series with a switch (Figure 9b) [219]. This configuration replicates the behavior of a cascaded transistor pair using a single device. Its structure, with separate injection and conduction control gates, enables biasing flexibility and circuit simplification [229–234]. The main design variables include the height of the barrier at the source, the degree of overlap between the source region and its associated gate (Figure 9c), and the geometry and permittivity of the dielectric and semiconductor (Figure 9d) in the source and channel regions [219, 222]. These parameters determine the injection efficiency, the saturation voltage, and the transconductance g_m profile, enabling either constant (Figure 9e) or exponential (Figure 9f) g_m by design.

With appropriate design, several behaviors emerge that are highly relevant to analog and neuromorphic computation. First, the linearity, and in particular a directly proportional dependence (Figure 9e), between the output current and the source gate bias can be maintained even when the device operates in saturation [219, 233]. This behavior results in low distortion and simultaneously high output resistance. Second, it allows precise control of signal amplitude via the source gate, while the conduction gate governs timing and enabling functions. The separation of amplitude (Figure 9g) and temporal (Figure 9h) domains make the MMT valuable in applications, such as micro-LED driving [232, 234] and sensor interfacing, as well as in energy-efficient analog computation [213].

2.4.1 | Multimodal Transistors in Neuromorphic and Brain-Inspired Computing

In neuromorphic architectures, local analog processing, embedded memory, and low-energy transfer functions are essential [235]. The MMT aligns naturally with these requirements. The source control gate can emulate synaptic weighting or analog

FIGURE 9 | (a) Structural representation of a multimodal transistor (MMT) architecture with current control gate (CG1) and channel control gate (CG2). (b) The MMT can be considered as an analog current source in series with a digital switch. (c) CG1 controls the amount of current in the source-CG1 overlap region S, while CG2 controls digital switching in the source-drain gap region d. S is a design parameter in MMTs, as well as (d) semiconductor and gate insulator layer thickness (t_s , t_i) and/or permittivity (ϵ_s , ϵ_i), which can be tailored to provide (e) directly proportional or (f) exponential dependence of drain current on CG1 voltage. The separation of analog charge injection in the source region from digital channel switching allows for implementing simultaneous (g) pulse amplitude and (h) pulse width modulation for micro-LED pixel driving. (i) Extremely compact digital-to-analog converters (DACs) can be designed, which enables (j) multiplying DAC (MDAC) operation when implemented with directly proportional dependence of drain current. (k) Floating gates allow for MMT functionality to extend into memory and neuromorphic computing paradigms. Adapted with permission from Ref. [225] and [232] under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 License.

memory, while the channel control gate acts as a neuronal threshold or enabling input [236]. These two interacting mechanisms form a physical analogy to the synapse-neuron pair, indicating a promising route to learning and activation at the device level without complex multi-transistor circuitry.

The engineered linearity of the MMT allows compact digital-to-analog conversion (DAC, Figure 9i) and multiplying DACs (MDACs), where bit significance can be defined both by the gated source width and by distinct gate voltages (Figure 9j) [219, 229].

The same mechanism enables the implementation of a rectified linear unit (ReLU) transfer characteristic [233], with practically zero output below a threshold and a linear response above it [234]. This behavior provides both the analog precision and the nonlinear response required for mixed-signal neuromorphic computation [235].

A further advantage arises from the decoupled effects of the MMT's input terminals. This enables the selective integration of analog memory, where one gated region can store a potential or

charge state while the other processes a separate dynamic signal (Figure 9k) [219]. Depending on the materials and structures used, this can yield volatile or non-volatile memory behavior. The addition of such a temporal dimension to computation supports event-driven processing in a way that mimics biological systems.

The structural simplicity of the MMT also enables significant circuit-level compactness. A single MMT can replace several conventional transistors, reducing the number of components for areal efficiency, but also interconnect complexity, for significant processing time and materials savings [231, 232]. This simplification improves yield and reduces cost in large-area manufacturing [234]. The resulting architectures are particularly suited for near-sensor processing, where local amplification, low distortion, and high energy efficiency are more valuable than high operating frequency [219]. The inherent current stability and low-voltage saturation that come from contact-controlled operation improves signal integrity even in disordered or flexible semiconductor systems [236, 237].

2.4.2 | Outlook and Challenges to Implementation for Multimodal Transistors

An important consideration for future progress is the integration of analog memory and synaptic functionality through compatible materials and voltage regimes. Floating-gate or charge-trapping elements, as well as ferroelectric and ionic semiconductors, offer promising routes for implementing learning and plasticity, while maintaining low power consumption. Because the MMT operates under contact control, there is an inherent trade-off between achieving a low drain-source saturation voltage and maintaining a manageably low gate bias range [222]. Low-voltage operation without loss of output current requires careful optimization of the barrier properties, the dielectric composition, and device geometry.

Although individual devices have already shown increased functionality, high intrinsic gain, and predictable nonlinearity, practical neuromorphic systems will require dedicated circuit demonstrations. Designing MMTs that act as functional neurons or synapses and validating their endurance and variability will be critical next steps. These efforts depend on close collaboration in device physics, materials science, and circuit design.

Industrial feasibility is encouraging. The MMT can be fabricated within existing large-area process flows with only minor adaptations [234]. It is compatible with thin-film silicon, oxide, organic, and hybrid semiconductor technologies. Display and image-sensor backplanes provide an ideal platform for early demonstration, as they already employ multi-gate geometries and require compact mixed-signal circuits. Penetration within these established manufacturing environments as a means of prototyping MMT circuits will bridge academic innovation with manufacturable technology.

It is essential to advance, in parallel, both directions of development: the conceptual exploration of bio-inspired analog computation and the scaling of industrial demonstrators that use multimodal transistors. Convergence between these two paths

will enable near-sensor, ultra-low-power signal processing hardware for distributed intelligent systems [219]. Applications may include lab-on-chip devices, biosensing, autonomous environmental monitors, wearable electronics, and implantable medical devices. Once matured, MMT technology has the potential to provide a new foundation for scalable, material-agnostic neuromorphic platforms that combine analog processing efficiency with thin-film manufacturability [221].

Arrays of MMTs are expected to scale well, with the addition of an additional set of gate lines and minimal, low complexity peripheral control circuitry. If device layout is carefully optimized, the MMT occupies roughly the same area as a conventional TFT, and gate-to-gate crosstalk minimization becomes a layout optimization exercise, in which circuit designers are already versed. Other practical limitations may be related to the trade-off between saturation voltage and gate-source voltage ranges, which can be optimized according to the requirements of the application, the capabilities of the technology, and the supply voltage limitations. From a power dissipation perspective, this adds little overhead, since gate dynamic gate switching events draw a relatively small proportion of total power, and optimizations biased toward reducing saturation voltage V_{DSAT} and output conductance may yield the greatest savings.

3 | A Unified Perspective on Neuromorphic Device Technologies

In this section, we provide a unified perspective on the key neuromorphic device families covered in this article (ferroelectric devices, organic electronic devices, 2D-material-based synaptic elements, and multimodal neuromorphic transistors) and summarize their underlying physical mechanisms responsible for respective neuromorphic functionality and their target application domains.

While these technologies offer compelling capabilities, each also presents characteristic failure modes and reliability challenges that must be addressed through appropriate stabilization strategies. As a general comment applicable across all material classes, greater effort is required to establish standardized characterization protocols for both device performance and durability. These aspects are also discussed here to give a coherent, cross-technology understanding of device performance and robustness, allowing readers to make informed judgments about device applicability.

3.1 | Device Technology Landscape for Intelligent Neuromorphic Hardware: Key Characteristics, Potential Failure Modes, and Stability Mechanisms

Despite the various advantages offered by ferroelectric neuromorphic devices such as nonvolatile multilevel analog states, low-energy voltage-driven programming, CMOS compatibility of FeFETs, and dense compute-in-memory capability in FeCAP crossbar arrays, several reliability challenges still limit their large-scale deployment. For instance, *Fatigue*, caused by interface charge trapping, defect accumulation, and domain pinning, gradually reduces switchable polarization during repeated cycling.

Imprint effects can arise from asymmetric interfaces, generating internal bias fields that shift the polarization switching characteristics and favor one switching direction causing eventual performance degradation. Moreover, HfO₂-based ferroelectrics often exhibit wake-up behavior, where remanent polarization increases during early cycles due to oxygen vacancy redistribution and the activation of previously pinned domains. Although this improves polarization initially, it introduces variability in early analog states. In addition, depolarization fields from incomplete charge screening can destabilize polarization, particularly in ultrathin films, leading to gradual drift of stored analog weights. For flexible platforms, mechanical bending introduces strain that can induce domain rotation, interfacial defects, or microcracks, degrading polarization stability. These challenges are typically addressed through optimized interfaces, dopant engineering, symmetric electrode stacks, and mechanically robust device structures to ensure stable long-term analog operation [32–34].

For organic neuromorphic devices, durability is as critical as peak performance. Their failure modes frequently mirror those of conventional organic electronics, with additional pathways tied directly to the physical processes that enable neuromorphic functionality. Electrical failures under sustained bias generally stem from electromigration, Joule heating, and electrochemical degradation. Electromigration, prominent under high fields and current densities, drives atomic or ionic displacement near contacts, leading to voids, aggregation, and increased resistance or shorts [238]. Joule heating induces morphological changes, film delamination, or thermal expansion mismatch between layers [239, 240], and can accelerate unwanted ion migration. Electrochemical reactions at electrodes or within the bulk cause threshold drift and memory-state degradation. The dominant failure mechanism depends strongly on applied stress and device architecture: MIM devices operating above ~10 V are most vulnerable to electromigration and thermal degradation, while low-voltage OECTs (<1 V) are primarily limited by ion accumulation, channel swelling, and parasitic electrochemical reactions.

Environmental exposure to water, oxygen, light, and heat further degrades organic devices by damaging electrodes, organic layers, dielectrics, and electrolytes. Light and thermal stress accelerate self-discharge and memory fading, particularly in OECTs and OFETs. Flexible and wearable platforms introduce additional mechanical failure modes, tension, bending, and cyclic fatigue, that lead to interfacial delamination, cracking, or conductivity loss due to stiffness mismatch across layers [241]. Thus, environmentally robust material design and encapsulation strategies (e.g., UV and thermal barriers) are critical, although they may introduce issues such as interlayer delamination or reduced fabrication yield. Mechanical patterning strategies, mesh layouts, kirigami structures, improve fatigue resistance, while interfacial engineering can stabilize electrical characteristics, enhance adhesion, and reduce moisture and oxygen ingress [242]. At the system level, fault-tolerant architectures with redundancy, error correction, and self-healing pathways further mitigate device-level failures [243].

Two-dimensional (2D) materials present a distinct set of reliability challenges, particularly due to the lack of standardized assessment protocols for long-term stability under realistic elec-

trical, mechanical, and environmental stress. Repeated switching can generate defect migration, contact degradation, and interfacial delamination, leading to conductance drift, variability, and eventual loss of switching or sensing. The weakest points are often the metal and dielectric layers rather than the 2D material itself. Highly reactive 2D materials, such as BP or MXenes, suffer from rapid oxidation and hydrolysis, while even more stable TMDCs gradually degrade when exposed to ambient conditions. These vulnerabilities are amplified in flexible formats, where encapsulation stacks can crack or craze under strain.

Although 2D materials possess exceptional intrinsic flexibility, device performance still degrades through mechanical fatigue, interface failure, and oxidation [244]. The 2D layer can tolerate large strain, but contacts and dielectrics often cannot. Consequently, strategies such as neutral-plane positioning, enhanced adhesion via plasma treatments or Ti/Cr interlayers, and grain-size engineering are widely adopted [245]. h-BN and ALD-grown dielectrics or ferroelectrics provide effective environmental barriers, particularly when deposited in situ. Low-temperature processing and precursor engineering remain crucial for mechanically stable flexible 2D-material devices.

A key opportunity lies in heterogeneous integration of multiple 2D materials, dielectrics, and metals in vertically stacked neuromorphic structures. Ideally, this should be achieved through in situ CVD or ALD growth, or through printing methods (spray, inkjet, screen printing) within a unified processing environment to avoid exposure to ambient contaminants. ALD is especially advantageous given its compatibility with diverse substrates, excellent film quality, and suitability for integrating complex heterostructures. Coupled with fault-tolerant neuromorphic architectures, these approaches will be essential for reliable in-memory and in-sensor computing on both flexible and rigid platforms.

From a device-architecture standpoint, multimodal transistors (MMTs) share many advantages with source-gated transistors (SGTs), which exhibit high robustness even in materials where conventional TFTs perform poorly. SGTs in amorphous and polycrystalline Si outperform TFTs under bias stress [246], and MMTs mitigate unwanted drain-current effects such as impact ionization via field-relief structures or reduced channel gate bias [247]. Organic SGTs show strong longevity under ambient storage because the source contact shields the injection region [248]. Even OTFTs with Ag contacts, typically stable, benefit from source-barrier modulation, as demonstrated in early Ag-contact OMMTs [249]. Thus, eliminating injection barriers entirely in organic electronics may be counterproductive when stability is a priority.

A cross-technology comparison (Table 2) reveals that each material and device family brings unique strengths that positions it most suitable for specific neuromorphic roles. For instance, Table 2 clearly shows that two-dimensional material-based devices provide ultrafast switching, atomically thin channels, optical nonlinearity, and compatibility with flexible and transparent substrates, yet suffer from variability, environmental degradation, and integration complexity and similarly, MMTs complement all three categories with compact circuitry and robustness, though their performance is limited by required source-gate overlap and contact-barrier inhomogeneity. Together,

TABLE 2 | Mapping of various neuromorphic device technologies and their physical/electrical characteristics to suitable application domains.

Device technology and related works	Physical switching mechanism	Electrical characteristics	Performance metrics	Key strengths	Key limitations	Target application domains
Ferroelectric devices [20–28, 29]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Polarization reversal via domain nucleation, growth, and pinning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Bipolar switching; ■ Non-volatile multilevel states; ■ extremely low leakage; ■ fast, energy-minimal voltage-driven updates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Endurance-10^8-10^9 ■ Retention->10-year ■ Linearity-high mostly under increasing voltage pulsing scheme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Voltage-driven switching, ultra-low static power; ■ selector-less operation, CMOS-compatible, Non-destructive readout possibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Fatigue, wake-up effects; ■ retention degradation under bending; ■ depolarization in ultra-thin FE layers; ■ mechanical microcracks in flexible substrates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Wearable devices, Event-driven autonomous systems, in-sensor vision/tactile-perception [250–254]
Organic neuromorphic devices [97–99, 114, 105, 130, 255–257]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Photo-electrochemical ■ Capacitive effect ■ Charge trapping ■ Filament 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Low operation voltage ■ Ionic conduction ■ Volumetric capacitance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Endurance: 10000 cycles [130] ■ Retention: 500 days [97, 98] ■ Linearity: $1 \cdot 10^6$ cd m⁻² [99] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Multimodal sensing ■ Biocompatibility ■ Flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stability and endurance ■ Compatibility to CMOS ■ Scalability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Vision/tactile/chemical perception [99, 114, 256, 257, 268] ■ Wearable devices [105] ■ Biointerfaces [255]

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Device technology and related works	Physical switching mechanism	Electrical characteristics	Performance metrics	Key strengths	Key limitations	Target application domains
2D Material neuromorphic devices [203–218]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defect migration, such as vacancies, ions etc. [258–260] Phase transition [261, 262] Filament formation [132, 263] Schottky emission (SE) and direct tunneling (DT) [264] Charge trapping [265] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bipolar and unipolar resistive switching Analog conductance tunability suitable for synaptic weight updates. Low operating voltages (sub-1 V) and femto Joule [132, 259, 266] switching energies due to atomically thin channels Ultrafast switching [266] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endurance – 10^7 switching cycles [258] Retention - 10^5 s [258] Nonlinearity for potentiation (β_p) and depression (β_d) is 0.55 and -1.00, respectively, and the symmetry between potentiation and depression, is 0.22 even under >700 bending cycles [202] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compatible with flexible, transparent, and heterogeneous integration Multimodal coupling CMOS backend compatibility and scalable growth (CVD, ALD, vdW stacking) enabling dense crossbars and multi-terminal neuromorphic circuits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variability in switching parameters Environmental instability for some 2D materials (e.g., BP, MXenes) and reliability concerns under repeated mechanical bending Poor adhesion between 2D material and flexible substrate—adhesion layers or plasma treatments can mitigate but also introduce additional defects and stress. Complex heterogeneous integration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inmemory and in-sensor neuromorphic computing [22, 23, 267] Flexible and wearable neuromorphic systems for biomedical monitoring, soft robotics, and onskin perception- [132, 202] Multimodal and optoelectronic neuromorphic platforms, such as neuromorphic vision sensors [269, 270]
Multimodal neuromorphic transistors [219–237]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Voltage/applied electric field 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CG1 modulates analog amount of current, CG2 controls digital switching. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low voltage operation; flat saturation; directly proportional linearity (by design) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power-efficient operation (low saturation voltage, low off-state leakage); technology agnosticism; circuit reduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires staggered-electrode configuration in source region; prone to barrier inhomogeneity; CG1 switching speed limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Display, analog front-ends, sensor/imaging arrays, hardware AI, edge computing, molecular imaging

these device classes map to distinct neuromorphic niches, and effective deployment will require coordinated advances in materials, interfaces, device architecture, encapsulation, and system-level design.

4 | Integrated Neuromorphic System Design: A Circuit-Level Perspective

The development of neuromorphic hardware has progressed from isolated demonstrations of individual memristive switching events into a sophisticated ecosystem of fully integrated systems capable of perception, learning, adaptation, and autonomous decision-making. Over the years, the field has matured into a multilayered stack in which sensing, computation, memory, and learning coexist in a hardware-efficient manner. Importantly, this transformation has not arisen solely from algorithmic advances but from deeply intertwined progress in materials, devices, circuits, architectures, and system-level implementations. To understand how neuromorphic hardware evolves from fundamental device physics into complete intelligent systems, one must analyze the technology from a circuit designer's viewpoint, because system-level intelligence emerges directly from the electrical behavior, temporal dynamics, and stochastic properties of the underlying devices [271]. The neuromorphic stack can be understood as a progression from device primitives to synaptic cells, compute-in-memory fabrics, neuron circuits, peripheral electronics, hardware-aware learning, associative learning engines, multimodal fusion modules, energy-autonomous operation, and probabilistic/security functions, all of which result from carefully orchestrated device-circuit co-design.

At the foundation of the neuromorphic hierarchy lie memristive and memcapacitive devices whose analog conductance or charge states serve as synaptic weights [272]. The switching behavior of these devices arises from ionic drift, oxygen vacancy migration, filament formation and rupture, amorphous-to-crystalline phase transitions, or ferroelectric polarization reversal, each mechanism governed by internal kinetics, activation energies, retention and fatigue characteristics, and intrinsic stochasticity [273–275]. These physical processes control the allowable write voltage window, the achievable conductance granularity, the linearity of weight updates, and the temporal stability of programmed states. As a result, device physics dictates what pulse waveforms, current limits, timing margins, and readout mechanisms circuit designers must implement. Thus, rather than imposing abstract neural algorithms onto arbitrary hardware, neuromorphic system architecture is fundamentally shaped by the physical constraints and opportunities provided by nanoscale devices themselves [276].

Building reliable synaptic cells requires circuit-level access structures that enforce controllability and protect devices from unintended state changes. In 1T1M and 1S1R architectures, a transistor or selector enables accurate current compliance and isolation, allowing robust programming at the cost of increased footprint [277]. In contrast, selectorless FeCAP and FeFET crosspoint arrays depend entirely on precise bias partitioning, most notably the V/3 scheme, to prevent half-select disturbance during write operations [277–279]. Implementing such schemes requires multi-rail high-voltage drivers, well-matched routing networks,

low-leakage analog switches, and synchronized timing so that only the targeted cell experiences the full switching field, while all remaining cells remain below their coercive voltage. These biasing strategies highlight how circuit design must actively counteract the intrinsic electrical interactions within dense crossbar arrays.

At the computational level, crossbar arrays serve as the physical substrate for performing vector-matrix multiplication operations, which are central to convolutional neural networks. When convolution kernels are mapped onto the crossbar in the form of conductance values, and sliding input patches are applied as voltage vectors to the rows, the resulting output currents along the columns correspond to the multiply-and-accumulate (MAC) operations defined by Ohm's and Kirchhoff's laws [280]. For deeper network layers, multi-array processing structures distribute computation across several crossbars, each generating partial sums that mixed-signal shift-and-add circuits combine before forwarding to subsequent stages. This architecture removes the traditional von Neumann bottleneck as computation is performed directly in the memory fabric, enabling highly parallel, energy-efficient inference that scales naturally with array size.

The analog currents emerging from these arrays flow into leaky-integrate-and-fire (LIF) neuron modules. These circuits convert continuous-valued analog signals into discrete spike trains through membrane integration, leakage, threshold detection, and reset dynamics implemented with RC networks, current mirrors, comparators, and operational transconductance amplifiers [281, 282]. The membrane time constant, $\tau = RC$, determines the temporal behavior of each neuron and must remain stable across process, voltage, and temperature corners to ensure consistent temporal filtering and firing behavior [283]. Moreover, the spike timing generated by these neuron circuits directly governs the timing of synaptic plasticity events, making the neuron block both computationally essential and temporally authoritative within the neuromorphic network [284].

Peripheral electronics play an equally critical role in maintaining accuracy and robustness across the system. Level shifters, high-voltage write drivers, analog-to-digital converters, transimpedance amplifiers, charge-sharing readouts, bootstrapped sampling switches, and programmable bias-routing matrices form the infrastructure that enables reliable analog and mixed-signal processing [285]. In FeCAP-based systems, nondestructive readout relies on isolating the ferroelectric capacitance and sharing its charge with a reference capacitor to extract the stored polarization state without triggering unintended switching [286]. These peripheral circuits determine the overall signal integrity, noise floor, conversion accuracy, latency, and energy consumption of the neuromorphic engine, thereby shaping system-level performance. Because physical crossbars are not ideal, they introduce device mismatch, IR drop, nonlinear state updates, parasitic coupling, and stuck-ON/OFF faults [287]. To ensure that neural networks remain robust across such irregularities, hardware-aware training, incorporates the device imperfections directly into the learning process. Models of noise, drift, perturbation (δW_{ij}), and fault masking are applied during forward and backward propagation so that the network learns weight configurations that match the behavior of the actual hardware

FIGURE 10 | End-to-End Neuromorphic Associative-Learning Pipeline for Real-Time Autonomous Driving, Multisensory Fusion, and Fault-Tolerant Vehicle Control using memristor-based mixed signal circuits. Partially adapted from [13] under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 License and partially reproduced with permission from [307].

array rather than an idealized mathematical model. The resulting trained weight matrix W' is thus inherently adapted to the underlying physical substrate, enabling reliable inference even in the presence of substantial device-level irregularities. Additionally, capacitive IMC have been proposed to replace resistive IMC to improve on issues like large IR drop, larger footprint, process complexity and cost for selector integration and so on [288–290].

Beyond CNN-style inference, memristive crossbars naturally support associative learning, since correlated sensory inputs tend to strengthen shared pathways through spike-timing-dependent plasticity or Hebbian-like mechanisms [291]. This allows neuromorphic circuits to encode stimulus–response associations, conditioned reflexes, reward–punishment dynamics, and context-sensitive behavioral adaptations directly in hardware. Associative learning enables a level of autonomy, energy-efficiency and adaptability that surpasses static inference models, allowing systems to evolve their responses over time in response to environmental interactions [292–294].

When multiple sensory modalities, such as vision, sound, touch, smell, vibration, radar, or inertial cues are encoded as spike trains, neuromorphic circuits can perform multimodal sensor fusion within the crossbar itself, without requiring digital preprocessing [295, 296]. The intrinsic analog summation of crossbars allows heterogeneous sensory signals to be blended into unified, correlated representations. This results in robust perception even when individual sensors are noisy, partially obstructed, or degraded, making neuromorphic sensor fusion extremely valuable for autonomous robotics, drones, vehicles, and embedded agents operating in uncertain environments (Figure 10) [13, 307].

Neuromorphic circuits are particularly well-suited for energy-autonomous operation because they are inherently sparse, event-driven, and analog. Their standby power is often negligible, and synaptic updates only occur during meaningful events, making them compatible with power harvested from photovoltaics, piezoelectrics, or thermoelectric sources [297]. Such systems can operate indefinitely on ambient energy, enabling long-term deployment in remote monitoring, wearable devices, environmental sensing platforms, and distributed IoT networks [298]. Associative-learning circuits are especially powerful in these contexts because they adapt without requiring energy-intensive training algorithms such as backpropagation.

Finally, the stochastic nature of many memristive devices opens pathways toward probabilistic computing and integrated hardware security. Devices exhibiting random switching dynamics can act as probabilistic bits, or p-bits, enabling Bayesian inference, Monte Carlo sampling, stochastic optimization, and uncertainty-aware decision-making directly in hardware [299, 300]. The same randomness can be exploited to generate physical unclonable functions (PUFs) and true random number generators (TRNGs), providing secure keys, authentication primitives, and encryption seeds without requiring separate cryptographic hardware [301, 302]. These capabilities allow neuromorphic systems to incorporate security and privacy protections inherently within their physical fabric.

On the learning side, designing learning algorithms that operate reliably on non-ideal analog devices requires explicitly modelling and exploiting device imperfections rather than treating them as nuisances. A practical strategy is hardware-aware training, where

device characteristics such as write noise, conductance drift, limited dynamic range, and asymmetric LTP/LTD behavior are incorporated directly into the training loop. For instance, when programming FeFET or FTJ synapses [23], the update function can be shaped to match device nonlinearity, and stochastic weight perturbations can be injected during training to emulate cycle-to-cycle variations. Similarly, for organic or 2D-material synapses with high variability, probabilistic learning rules, such as stochastic Hebbian updates or reinforcement-based pulse modulation, can improve convergence by aligning algorithmic plasticity with physical switching statistics. In spiking systems, bounded weight dynamics, error-triggered consolidation, and meta-learning rules that adapt to drift can provide additional robustness. A concrete example is drift-aware STDP, where the device's natural relaxation is treated as a biological forgetting mechanism, reducing the need for explicit refresh cycles [291, 292].

Beyond individual learning rules, evaluating neuromorphic systems demands holistic energy and reliability metrics that reflect real operating conditions rather than idealized per-device numbers. System-level energy must account for not only synaptic updates but also peripheral operations, address decoding, sensing, charge redistribution, ADC/DAC overhead, and communication across arrays. For example, a FeCAP-based crossbar may achieve femtojoule-level switching energy per synapse, but the effective energy per classification could be dominated by ADC sampling or wordline/bitline charging [278, 279]. More comprehensive evaluation therefore reports energy per inference, energy per training iteration, and energy breakdowns by subsystem. Reliability must likewise be assessed at the system level, considering device drift, write noise, stuck-on/off failures, and mechanical degradation in flexible platforms. Techniques such as Monte Carlo fault injection, on-chip redundancy, error-tolerant coding, and periodic recalibration can be evaluated in simulation and confirmed experimentally. A useful example is testing an SNN classifier under increasing fractions of dead or drifting synapses to determine the system's fault-tolerance envelope, or benchmarking classification accuracy over time as FeFET thresholds or 2D-material defects evolve. Together, these approaches enable neuromorphic hardware to be designed, trained, and evaluated in a manner that accounts for the full spectrum of device non-idealities and system overheads, ultimately leading to architectures that remain robust, energy-efficient, and reliable under real-world operating conditions.

Taken together, the blocks involved in compute-in-memory crossbars, multi-array accumulation structures, LIF neurons, mixed-signal peripheral circuitry, and hardware-aware training, form the backbone of a neuromorphic computing engine. When further combined with associative learning, multimodal sensor fusion, ambient energy harvesting, and probabilistic and secure computing functionalities, these components evolve into fully integrated neuromorphic systems capable of sensing, interpreting, learning, adapting, securing, and autonomously operating in real-world environments. This holistic view demonstrates that neuromorphic intelligence is fundamentally a hardware achievement grounded in device behavior and circuit innovation, rather than merely an algorithmic abstraction [303, 304].

5 | Future Perspective

In summary, a variety of emerging memristive devices demonstrate significant potential for applications in neuromorphic computing tactile sensing, and optoelectronics, largely because of their capacity to efficiently simulate neuronal and synaptic functions while enabling real-time, low-power decision-making. However, their integration in large-scale networks is still critically limited by concerns of reliability and scalability. This includes significant device-to-device and cycle-to-cycle variability, limited endurance in filamentary devices, unstable switching behavior like V_T shift, and thermal or other environmental sensitivity. Therefore, before constructing robust and scalable neuromorphic architectures, these issues need to be addressed by consistent efforts for fabricating and testing new material stacks, as discussed in this perspective.

Relying on experimental and simulation data, authors strongly believe that future progress in neuromorphic systems will center on enabling truly scalable and energy-efficient architectures. To be particular, the advances in ferroelectric materials, suggest that upcoming innovations may include 3D ferroelectric crossbars, hybrid ferroelectric-CMOS compute tiles, and learning rules that directly exploit their multilevel analog programmability. These directions aim to overcome current bottlenecks related to variability, wake-up behavior, and scaling limits, while pushing ferroelectrics toward reliable, high-density in-memory computing. Organic neuromorphic technologies will advance through molecularly engineered semiconductors and electrolytes, improved encapsulation, ion-confined device architectures, and hybrid organic-inorganic stacks. Equally important are learning algorithms designed to operate robustly with the intrinsic stochasticity of organic analog states. Addressing persistent challenges like yield, long-term stability, parasitic ionic drift, and mechanical fatigue, will be essential to transition organic neuromorphic systems from flexible prototypes to deployable, large-area intelligent sensor networks. In 2D-material neuromorphic devices, the path forward relies on precise defect and phase control, effective passivation and encapsulation, optimized metal-semiconductor contact resistances, and wafer-scale or transfer-free synthesis compatible with low-temperature BEOL processing. These advances are foundational for realizing dense crossbar arrays, van der Waals heterostructures, and multimodal in-sensor and in-memory computing elements. Stable and reproducible analog behavior in atomically thin channels remains the critical barrier, and opportunity, for this technology class. Multimodal transistors (MMTs) provide a valuable complement to all these material systems by enabling compact, robust circuit blocks in regimes where conventional TFTs underperform. Their controlled injection characteristics and resilience to bias stress are promising, yet improvements in source-gate overlap design, switching speed, and interface uniformity are necessary. Broader adoption will require systematic device qualification, reliable AC models, and incorporation into established design toolkits.

Across all device families, the ultimate determinant of impact will be full-stack hardware integration. Peripheral circuits for addressing, bias generation, sensing, calibration, and data conversion often dominate overall area and power. Meaningful system-level gains therefore require materials, devices, circuits,

TABLE 3 | Application spectrum of neuromorphic applications and the corresponding device mechanisms.

Application Domain	Underlying Device Behavior	Circuit/System Example	Representative Works
Synaptic weight storage & STDP learning	Analog multilevel conductance modulation	Crossbar arrays for VMM and adaptive inference	[302–305]
Associative learning & decision-making	Non-linear state transition; STDP correlation	3D or hybrid memristor–CMOS associative circuits	[13, 306–308]
Sensor fusion & contextual perception	Photo-/chemo-responsive switching; reservoir dynamics	MoTe ₂ optoelectronic in-sensor fusion arrays	[309–311]
Bio-implant & wearable neuromorphic devices	Flexible oxide/polymer memristors	EEG/EMG classifiers; adaptive prosthetic controllers	[102, 312]
Probabilistic & stochastic computing	Diffusive/threshold filament dynamics; random switching	p-bit networks; Bayesian inference hardware	[313]
Hardware security & trustworthy AI	Device variability; stochastic cycle-to-cycle behavior	PUF/TRNG integrated neuromorphic platforms	[314, 315]

and architectures to be co-optimized rather than developed in isolation. Only through such coordinated, end-to-end co-design can neuromorphic hardware achieve the density, reliability, and energy efficiency required for real-world intelligent systems. Apart from device physics and substrate level innovation, for an integrated neuromorphic hardware system, adaptation of some architecture-level strategies is essential. For example, spike encoding and decoding are used as distinct modules in current neuromorphic tactile systems, which are typically implemented using independent device arrays and circuits coupled in a board-level design. Although these modular approaches are appropriate for proof-of-concept demonstrations, fragmented sensing, encoding, and processing can limit system efficiency for improved architectural cohesiveness. The system's scalability is ultimately limited by the physically isolated systems, which also add connectivity overhead, synchronization challenges, and extra power expenses. Future research should concentrate on developing better integration solutions, where sensors, interface electronics, analog processing units, and their powering module are all co-designed and co-fabricated within unified hardware platforms, to overcome these constraints. Realizing real-time, energy-efficient, and dependable neuromorphic systems appropriate for wearable and autonomous robots would require such monolithic integration, backed by scalable and stable device technologies.

Also, it is important to note that collaborative mechanisms between these novel devices and traditional computing units need to work better to fully realize the potential of novel devices. On the software side, new hardware-compatible algorithms and programming models need development to fully leverage the advantages of the new devices in brain-inspired computing and sensing.

Table 3 gives an overview of major neuromorphic computing application domains and the corresponding device mechanisms, circuit/system implementations, and representative works. The table illustrates how diverse physical switching behaviors, ranging from analog conductance modulation to stochastic filament dynamics, enable features like synaptic learning, associative learning, sensor fusion, biomedical interfaces, probabilistic computing, and hardware security in memristive-based architectures.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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